

A DIGITAL TWIN SYSTEM FOR RETAIL INVENTORY & SALES MANAGEMENT

From conceptual architecture to a functional AI-enhanced prototype

Lappeenranta–Lahti University of Technology LUT

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ABSTRACT

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Effective inventory and sales management is crucial in the physical retail stores, directly impacting operational efficiency, customer satisfaction and cost. Integration of Digital Twin technology along with AI and RFID offers significant potential for optimise these functions. While a considerable amount of research has concentrated on Digital Twin development for supply chain management, its application in integrated and privacy-conscious retail & sales management systems is still remains a developing area. Thus, this thesis focuses on designing and developing a conceptual Digital Twin system to address this gap. The thesis begins with a comparative analysis of current inventory management systems as a foundational study. It then presents a conceptual DT architecture that integrates RFID and simulated Point of Sale (POS) data for a physical retail store. The core contribution of the thesis is the functional DT prototype validated using simulated data and demonstrated in a Unity-based 3D virtual environment. In addition, the system integrates simulated AI models (SMA, WMA, and LR) to reflect demand forecasting and automated inventory alerts. The findings of the research revealed that the proposed RFID-enabled DT system is capable of offering transformative business insights and privacy-conscious system for physical retail stores, bridging a critical gap in current retail operations.

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DECLARATIONS

Turnitin

The Originality of this thesis has been reviewed using the Turnitin similarity checking system.

AI usage

The author, Isuru Hollupathirage, takes full responsibility for the content of this thesis and has reviewed and edited the content generated by the possible use of AI tools.

SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Greek characters

α	Incidence angle
λ	Scaling factor
β	Regression coefficient
δ	Safety buffer
Λ	Combined adjustment factor
τ	Future index day
ω	Weight

Subscripts

i	Product index
t	Current date
$t - k$	Time Lag
k	Lag Period
s	Store
w	Warehouse
<i>base</i>	Baseline
<i>final</i>	Final result
<i>target</i>	Target
<i>seasonal</i>	Seasonal
<i>max</i>	Maximum

Superscripts

^ Forecast value

Abbreviations

AI Artificial Intelligence

ASGI Asynchronous Server Gateway Interface

AR Augmented Reality

BOM Bill of Materials

CAD Computer-Aided Design

CNN Convolutional Neural Network

DT Digital Twin

IoT Internet of Things

EOQ Economic Order Quantity

FMCG Fast Moving Consumer Goods

GDPR General Data Protections Regulation

LR Linear Regression

LSTM Long Short-Term Memory

NASA National Aeronautics and Space Administration

OOS Out of Stock

POS Point of Sale

PLM Product Lifecycle Management

PRISMA Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta Analyses

RFID Radio Frequency Identification

RBAC	Role Base Access Control
ROI	Return on Investment
SMA	Simple Moving Average
SME	Small and Medium Entreprises
SMTP	Simple Mail Transfer Protocol
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management
SoS	System of System
USD	United States Dollar
WMA	Weighted Moving Average
ZTNA	Zero Trust Network Access

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1 Introduction

The retail sector includes all the stores and shops that sell products or goods directly to the final consumer (Singh et al., 2022). The global retail market reached USD 23.00 Trillion in 2024, and it's expected to reach a value of USD 40.42 Trillion in 2034 (Expert Market Research, 2022). The retail sector is highly competitive with players ranging from large, multinational chains to SMEs and physical stores to online e-commerce platforms. Amidst the hyper-competitive retail landscape, physical retail stores face various challenges.

A significant challenge faced by physical retail stores is competing against the inventory transparency and personalised shopping experience provided by e-commerce, a competitive disadvantage that was exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic. Further, store managers and employees face challenges concerning when to restock shelves to avoid loss of sales, prevent overstocking which leads to waste, and optimal product placement strategy for store layout (Kümpel et al., 2021). Thus, Digital Twins (DT) solutions can help physical retail stores to enhance their operations, increase sales, and deliver superior customer experience through real-time data integration, advanced analytics, store layout optimisation, inventory management, predicting future issues and proposing alternative solutions.

Despite the vast benefits provided by DT, they can pose substantial privacy concerns through extensive data collection and unauthorised customer surveillance. Hence, to mitigate this, the proposed DT focuses on compliance with General data Protection Regulation (GDPR). It is designed to monitor inventory and shelves status using aggregate sales data, avoiding deliberate individual customer behaviour tracking.

1.1 Digital Twins

This section explores the theoretical foundations of the Digital Twins, beginning with its historical developments followed by various types, categories and fundamental components.

1.1.1 History of Digital Twins

Digital Twin is a virtual replica of an object, system, or structure that provides real-time data on the entity it represents. Although the term “Digital Twin” is new, the foundational concept can be traced back to the NASA Apollo programme. Following a catastrophic oxygen tank explosion incident during Apollo 13 in 1970s, NASA engineers used ground-based simulators and identical equipment of the spacecraft with real-time data to evaluate the situation and formulate an appropriate response strategy (McDonough, 2025).

David Gelernter, an American computer scientist and professor at Yale University, published a book entitled “Mirror Worlds” in 1992, which also discusses concepts foundational to Digital Twin models. In Chapter 1, he describes “Mirror Worlds” as follows:

“They are software models of some chunk of reality, some piece of the real world going on outside your window. Oceans of information pour endlessly into the model (through a vast maze of software pipes and hoses): so much information that the model can mimic reality's every move, moment-by-moment.” (Gelernter, 1992)

Gelernter (1992) provides examples of practical applications of the mirror world in aircraft, hospitals, cities, companies, and manufacturing processes (Emmert-Streib, 2023).

However, Dr. Michael Grieves is widely accepted as the creator of the Digital Twin concept.

Figure 1. Original Digital Twin Concept (Grieves, 2022)

Figure 1. shows the initial DT concept developed by Grieves (2002) for Product Lifecycle Management, but the term “Digital Twin” was first coined by John Vickers of NASA (Piascik et al., 2010) and was later popularised globally.

Figure 2. Digital Twin Model as explained by Grieves (Grieves, 2022)

Grieves (2022) explains the Digital Twin as a model with three main elements, as shown in Figure 2:

“an actual or intended physical element on the left side that currently exists or will exist in the physical world (the “Physical Twin”), the virtual or digital counterpart on the right side that exists in the virtual or digital world (“the Digital Twin”), and the communication channel of data and information between these two elements (the “Digital Thread”)”. (Grieves, 2022)

Subsequent definitions of Digital Twin also emphasise the dynamic and adaptive nature of DTs. Some of these definitions are given below:

“a living model of the physical asset or system, which continually adapts to operational changes based on the collected online data and information, and can forecast the future of the corresponding physical counterpart” (Liu et al., 2018)

“A Digital Twin is a dynamic and self-evolving digital/virtual model or simulation of a real-life subject or object (part, machine, process, human, etc.) representing the exact state of its physical twin at any given point in time via exchanging real-time data as well as keeping the historical data. It is not just the Digital Twin which mimics its physical twin, but any changes in the Digital Twin are mimicked by the physical twin too” (Singh et al., 2021).

“Digital Twin is a virtual, dynamic model in the virtual world that is fully consistent with its corresponding physical entity in the real world and can simulate its physical counterpart’s characteristics, behaviour, life, and performance in a timely fashion” (Zhuang et al., 2018).

The Digital Twin concept has now developed further with IoT, AI, AR & VR technologies across various industries. Each domain makes use of the DT concept in different ways (Crespi et al., 2023). The importance and the success of the Digital Twin concept rely on the possibility of moving many aspects of products, objects and entities from the physical to a software domain (Crespi et al., 2023). Hence, Digital Twin is an enabler for “softwarization” and “servitization” (Crespi et al., 2023), resulting in its widespread use to address various problems in many domains.

1.1.2 Types of Digital Twins

Digital Twin categorisation criteria vary in the literature. Crespi et al. (2023) categorise Digital Twins broadly into two main types.

i. Passive representations of physical objects:

These are based on real objects and support modelling and representation as logical replicas. They can be utilised to study and predict the behaviour of a physical object under particular conditions. This is the most common approach.

ii. Active representations of physical objects:

These can change or affect the behaviour of the physical object via two-way communication, allowing a DT to influence the behaviour of a physical object to achieve required optimisation and improvements in the physical processes.

Another categorisation of Digital Twins is based on a system’s lifecycle phase (Grieves, 2019) as follows.

i. Digital Twin Prototype (DTP):

The comprehensive design of the Digital Twin with all its variants. According to Grieves (2019), DTP should exist for all sophisticated manufactured products. DTP contains all the essential data required to create a physical copy, such as BOM (Bill of Materials), design files, CAD models, etc (Singh et al., 2021). Further, DTP is the initial phase of the product cycle and can be used for testing, including destructive scenarios, before creating a physical prototype (Singh et al., 2021). Once DTP is validated, a physical twin can be developed.

ii. Digital Twin Instance (DTI):

DTI is the digital instance that remains linked to an individual physical product throughout its life (Grieves & Vickers, 2017). However, as per Grieves (2019), DTI exists only for products where it is important to have information about that product throughout its life. Such as, aeroplanes, rockets, manufacturing floor equipment, and automobiles (Grieves, 2019).

iii. Digital Twin Aggregates (DTAs):

DTA represents an aggregate collection of multiple DTIs, providing both longitudinal and latitudinal representations of behaviour (Grieves, 2019). While longitudinal values correlate previous state changes with subsequent behavioural outcomes, latitudinal value occurs via a learning process which can be conveyed to the rest of the DTIs (Grieves, 2019). Longitudinal value enables the prediction of component failure when certain sensor data occurs (Grieves, 2019).

Figure 3 shows an example of DTI and DTA use in interaction, prediction, and learning as described by Grieves (2019).

Figure 3. DTI and DTA use in interrogation, prediction, and learning (Grieves, 2019)

Moreover, Tao et al. (2019) divide Digital Twins based on the scale involved in manufacturing. Accordingly, DTs can be divided into three different levels based on a hierarchy in the manufacturing sector (Figure 4).

i. Unit Level:

The smallest unit in manufacturing. It's based on the geometric, functional, behavioural, and operational model of a Unit Level physical twin (Singh et al., 2021). Hence, these DTs can be a piece of equipment or a component.

ii. System Level:

A combination of Unit Level DTs into a production system constitutes a System Level DT. There is a wider flow of data and better resource allocation at the System Level due to the higher level of interconnectivity and collaboration among multiple unit-level DTs. While production lines, shop floors, and factories can be considered System Level, a complicated product like an aircraft can also be considered as a System Level DT (Singh et al., 2021).

iii. System of Systems (SoS) Level:

When multiple System Level DTs are combined, they can be categorised as SoS Level DT. Thus, they integrate across enterprises or departments such as supply chain, design, service, maintenance, etc.

Figure 4. Hierarchical Levels of DT in Manufacturing (Singh et al., 2021)

Consequently, Digital Twins can be categorised into various types based on their characteristics, stages, hierarchy, etc.

1.1.3 Components of Digital Twins

Digital Twins primarily consist of three components. They are (1) physical reality, (2) virtual representation, and (3) interconnections that exchange information between the physical reality and virtual representation (VanDerHorn & Mahadevan, 2021) as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Digital Twin Components (VanDerHorn & Mahadevan, 2021)

The following section further explains these three components.

i. Physical reality

Physical reality encompasses the entire system, both known and unknown. VanDerHorn & Mahadevan (2021) further break down physical reality into three elements: physical system, physical environment and physical processes.

The physical system is a unification or group of interacting and interrelated entities delineated by boundaries in space and time. While traditionally, physical systems were considered man-made they can also be some aspect of the natural environment or the human body since Digital Twins are now expanded into healthcare, agricultural and environmental contexts. These can range from individual components such as machinery parts to complex integrated systems like whole manufacturing assets.

Physical Environment is the external conditions and influences surrounding the Physical System. Physical Systems interact with the environment through physical processes. The boundary between the physical system and environment varies for each DT application. For example, a DT of additive manufacturing. Here 3D printer is the physical system, while

room temperature, air flow, ambient vibration, etc, are the physical environment. Further, these relevant environmental parameters would be recorded and represented in the virtual space in order to allow for simulations, forecasts, and decisions to be made, which will impact the physical system of interest (VanDerHorn & Mahadevan, 2021).

Physical processes describe the way a system expresses itself in the physical environment and are the mechanism by which the entities of the system undergo changes in state (VanDerHorn & Mahadevan, 2021). In manufacturing, these may be casting, forging, welding, etc. Similar to physical systems and environments, physical processes are also represented in the virtual space for simulations, optimisation, and forecasting purposes.

ii. Virtual representation

Virtual representation in a Digital Twin captures the idea that the entity in the virtual space is merely a representation of an idealised form of the physical reality (VanDerHorn & Mahadevan, 2021). This is the core digital model of the physical reality, developed as an idealised representation in order to utilise for use cases. Thus, virtual representation is not an exact replica. There are mainly two elements used to develop the virtual representation. They are data, behaviour models, and a core component.

Due to the idealisation of the physical reality, abstraction is inevitable. Consequently, this results in the use of data models and/or behaviour models. While data model refers to a data structure that retains all the variables describing the reality at the level of abstraction chosen, behaviour models refer to the computational models that describe how the variables of interest relate to each other (VanDerHorn & Mahadevan, 2021). Likewise, according to Figure 6, the process of consistently transforming data from reality into a virtual representation, which provides evidence about reality is called the “interpretation process” (VanDerHorn & Mahadevan, 2021).

Figure 6. Data Abstraction Process (VanDerHorn & Mahadevan, 2021)

Any virtual representation consists of three main core components as described below:

- **Virtual system:** This is the primary component of the virtual representation and contains the data and models of the entities of interest from the physical system at a chosen level of abstraction (VanDerHorn & Mahadevan, 2021).
- **Virtual environment:** This is the virtual representation of the physical environment based on the chosen level of abstraction.
- **Virtual processes:** These are the computational models of the corresponding physical processes that simulate how the system changes over time, enabling “what-if” scenarios, forecasts and optimisations.

iii. Interconnections between physical reality and virtual representation

This is the final component of the DT, which depicts the bidirectional link that allows data and information to flow between the physical reality and its virtual representation. These bidirectional connections are twofold: the ‘physical to-virtual connection’ and the ‘virtual-to-physical connection’.

Physical to virtual connection is the process of data collection from the physical reality to update the states maintained in the virtual representation. It involves three steps:

- Collection of relevant information, including the direct measurement of the physical reality.
- Processing and interpretation of the collected data to a level that aligns with the abstraction of the virtual representation.
- Updating the states of the virtual representation using “state estimation” and “information fusion techniques” to infer states that cannot be measured and reduce levels of uncertainty.

The virtual-to-physical connection is the process of transferring information from the virtual representation back to the physical reality (VanDerHorn & Mahadevan, 2021), which closes the loop in the Digital Twin.

This process allows the insights and decisions generated through the virtual representation to be realised in the physical system via two methods:

- Through actions that result in a change in the physical system states
- Through actions that collect additional information from the physical system to further update the virtual representation

In a nutshell, a Digital Twin can be recognised as a sophisticated, interconnected system based upon physical reality, its virtual representation, and the interconnections between them. This facilitates a continuous flow of data, enabling an advanced, powerful real-time monitoring tool for data-driven decision-making, sophisticated simulations and future forecasts.

1.2 Retail Inventory Management Systems

Retail inventory management refers to a process that includes various operations such as managing stock levels, order management and inventory analysis. These processes collectively enable consumers to procure the desired merchandise from the retail store (Mr Bankim R. Vaja). Currently, many businesses in the retail sector face multiple challenges, especially in poor resource management and planning. Therefore, effective inventory management has become an essential factor in the retail industry (R. Ishfaq, G. Hançerlioğullar).

Furthermore, the growing competitive global market requires technological adaptation to improve operations and maximise profit. Among the various technologies, smart inventory management systems have emerged as a key solution for the retail sector. The revolution of Industry 4.0 has introduced new concepts with the integration of IoT, cyber-physical systems, cognitive computing and virtual reality (Perera, 2013; Vidhya, 2016). As a result of these technologies, the retail industry has adopted smart shelves and robotics to enhance the shopping experience (Liu, 2006).

1.3 Radio Frequency Identification

Radio Frequency Identification or RFID is a wireless technology that provides Automatic Identification and Data Capture (AIDC) using radio waves (Haibi, 2018). It is a widely used IoT technology in different sectors, such as supply chain management (SCM), healthcare sector, transportation, and IoT applications among others. There are three types of RFID tags, and they are categorised by their power sources, including passive, active and semi-passive (Figure 7).

RFID Tag Comparison: Chart					
Type	Range	Power	Cost	Cost	Use Case
 Passive	1-10 m	No Battery	Battery	\$\$	Item Tracking
 Active	30-150 m	No Battery	Battery	\$\$\$	Asset Tracking
 Semi-Passive	10-30 m	Battery	Battery	\$\$	Cold Chain

Figure 7. RFID Tag Comparison (Tirihima, 2024)

These three types of tags can be described as follows:

i. Passive tags

Passive tags are widely used in the retail sector for real-time product tracking. Consequently, these tags are more affordable than the other two types and do not require a power source or maintenance. Instead, they capture energy from the electromagnetic field generated by the RFID readers. When a tag receives a signal from the reader, the chip is powered to transmit stored data to the reader within a range of 1 to 10 metres. The lifespan of a passive tag lasts between 8 to 10 years. The tag durability depends on the physical tag material and environmental exposure, as it doesn't contain any power source.

ii. Active tags

Active tags are used for long-range tracking, from 30 to 150 metres. This tag is equipped with an on-board battery that powers both the tag and its transmitter. Active tags are expensive and perfect for real-time location tracking, because it does not require direct

reader interaction as they emit signals at regular intervals autonomously. This tag is ideal for long-range monitoring, particularly in outdoor or industrial environments.

iii. Semi-passive tags

Semi-passive tags serve as a combination of passive and active technologies. This tag also features an internal battery to power the circuits, but does not actively transmit a signal continuously. Rather, it only activates when queried by a reader, resulting in a better signal and performance covering up to 30 metres. Furthermore, this tag is mid-range in price and mainly used for detailed condition tracking (e.g. temperature, humidity).

RFID technology operates across several radio frequencies, including Low Frequency (LF), High Frequency (HF), Near Field Communication (NFC) and Ultra High Frequency (UHF). Each of these frequencies has unique characteristics suited to different purposes, as stated in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of RFID frequencies

RFID	Read range	Strengths	Limitations	Use Cases
LF- 30 KHz to 300 KHz	Up to 10 cm.	High resistance to water and metal interference.	Limited range and slow data transfer.	Animal tracking, industrial Machinery and automotive Applications.
HF- 3 MHz to 30 MHz	Up to 1 meter.	Large memory and stable read range.	Limited range compared to UHF.	Smart cards, ticketing systems, access control, and asset tracking.
NFC – subset of HF at 13.56 MHz	Up to 10 cm.	Two-way interaction and mobile-friendly.	One-to-one tag reading and limited scalability.	Contactless payments, consumer electronics and interactive marketing.
UHF – 300 MHz to 3 GHz	Up to 12 meters.	Rapid reading capability, long range and bulk reading.	Metal and liquid can cause interference.	Logistics, retail inventory and warehouse management.

The appropriate RFID solution is crucial and depends on the environmental factors and operational needs. Therefore, the wrong choice can result in system failure and replacement costs. Selecting the most suitable solution ensures reliable performance, scalability and a long lifespan.

1.4 Problem Statement

Physical retail stores face a significant comparative disadvantage against e-commerce due to a lack of real-time visibility of shelf stock levels, leading to stockouts and overstocking, and a lack of information on optimal product placements and layout arrangements, resulting in lost sales opportunities. While Digital Twins technology presents many potential implications to improve existing inventory and sales management systems in physical stores, currently, research and technological developments are largely concentrated around supply chain management and logistics. Furthermore, the existing in-store customer analytics and behaviour analytics technologies mostly rely on aggressive customer tracking and surveillance, leading to critical privacy concerns under GDPR frameworks. Therefore, a clear unexplored area is still prevalent in the retail sector, which requires solutions to bridge the gap between physical and digital retail environments that are both operationally and ethically aligned. Accordingly, this research aims to address this gap by proposing a privacy-conscious DT system leveraging RFID and AI models to automate inventory tracking, optimise shelf performance and store layout.

1.5 Research Objectives

- 1) To conduct a comparative analysis on existing retail inventory management systems and RFID-enabled solutions to establish a foundational understanding.
- 2) To design a conceptual Digital Twin architecture integrating RFID and POS data for real-time shelf monitoring and virtual representation.
- 3) To develop a functional prototype featuring virtual product placement optimisation using sales-based heatmaps of shelves and virtual layout testing through a Unity simulation environment.
- 4) To construct simulated AI models for demand forecasting and an automated inventory alert system to enhance operational efficiency within the prototype.

1.6 Research Scope

The focus of this thesis is to design and develop a Digital Twin solution based on RFID and POS data for a physical retail store. Following a comparative analysis of existing retail management systems, the architecture design and prototype specification constitute the main contribution. Furthermore, this includes proof-of-concept DT prototype development using synthetic data. It focuses on in-store operations such as layout management, real-time shelf monitoring, inventory management, and AI forecasting.

This thesis is organised into seven chapters and begins by introducing the fundamentals of Digital Twins, retail inventory management systems, RFID and other technologies, followed by the research problem and objectives, scope of the research in Chapter 1. The second chapter includes a systematic literature review using the PRISMA protocol to evaluate existing retail inventory systems, including Manual, Barcode, IoT, RFID and AI-driven approaches. Chapter three focuses on the conceptual Digital Twin architecture design for a retail enterprise. Chapter four documents the development of a functional DT prototype, integrated with a simulated SQLite database and AI models (SME, WMA, LR), which offers visualisations for stock levels, sales heatmaps, low-stock alerts, as well as AI recommendations. In Chapter 5, research findings are analysed and their implications discussed in the context of the existing literature. Chapter six concludes the thesis and offers suggestions for future enhancements. Finally, Chapter Seven acknowledges the constraints and limitations encountered during the research.

2 Comparative Analysis of Existing Retail Inventory Management Systems

In the retail sector, inventory & sales management play a critical role. The efficiency of the inventory management system used by stores determines a store's success by directly impacting smooth operations, customer satisfaction, costs, and overall agility. Thus, inventory & sales management systems have evolved significantly from rudimentary manual methods to advanced technological systems.

This chapter presents a comparative analysis of existing retail inventory management systems. The objective is to synthesise current literature and case studies to identify and compare advantages, disadvantages and overall impacts of each retail inventory management system.

2.1 Methodology for Comparative Analysis

This comparative analysis was conducted as a systematic literature review to achieve the objective of comparing existing retail inventory management systems and RFID-enabled solutions. According to Kitchenham & Charters (2007), a systematic literature review is a means of evaluating and interpreting all of the available research related to a certain research question, topic area, or phenomenon of interest. Comparative analysis was conducted according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) protocol (Page et al., 2021) to avoid biases as much as possible.

The methodology of the review consists of four phases as described in the following sections.

2.1.1 Step I: Search strategy and identification of literature

The initial literature search was conducted across IEEE Xplore and ScienceDirect using a combination of keywords and Boolean operators to filter the relevant literature. Comprehensive search strings were created using combinations of relevant keywords and Boolean operators (AND, OR) as given in Table 2. Open access Journal articles, peer-

reviewed articles, empirical case studies, conference proceedings, and published theses have been used for the review.

Table 2. Search term Booleans with the number of literature articles identified from 2015-2025

Search Term Boolean used	# of Open Access Articles identified	
	ScienceDirect	IEEE Xplore
("inventory management" OR "stock management") AND ("retail sector" OR "retail")	1,129	459
"inventory management" AND "retail" AND "digital systems"	34	3
("RFID" OR "radio frequency identification") AND ("retail" OR "inventory")	18	54
"Digital Twins" AND "retail" AND "inventory"	237	0
("AI" OR "Artificial Intelligence") AND ("inventory management" OR "inventory")	191	164
"Artificial Intelligence" AND "inventory management" AND ("RFID" OR "radio frequency identification")	271	7
"prototype" AND "retail inventory"	4	0

The search was limited to publications from 2015 to 2025 to include the most up-to-date technology. The initial search yielded a total of 2,751 records from IEEE Xplore and ScienceDirect. However, after considering the most relevant search terms results, 64 IEEE articles and 564 ScienceDirect articles were selected for further review.

2.1.2 Step II: Screening and selection

The screening process was conducted according to the PRISMA four-phase flow as per Figure 8. During the screening stage, relevant studies were recognised using titles and abstract reviews focusing on the following criteria:

- Literature reviews of inventory studies
- Inventory & sales prototypes development or case studies
- Inventory management technologies and inventory software development

- Quantitative performance analysis of inventory systems
- Retail inventory & sales systems

Figure 8. PRISMA Four-Phase Flow Diagram of the Screening Process

Studies focused solely on the supply chain, manufacturing systems, and exclusively on business and management theories of inventory systems were excluded from the comparative analysis. Further, publications that were not available online and not in the English language were also excluded. To refine the selection further, technological relevancy was considered. Accordingly, 27 mostly relevant papers were selected for the comparative analysis.

2.1.3 Step III: Data gathering and categorisation

In order to systematically synthesise the data literature papers data extraction matrix was created using Microsoft Excel, aiming to capture descriptive, technological, and empirical concepts in the papers. The columns of the extraction matrix are as below:

- A. Bibliography: Full reference of the paper
- B. Citation: For in-text comparison analysis

- C. Inventory system described: Specific inventory system or technology described in the paper; e.g., Manual, Barcode, RFID, AI, IOT etc.,
- D. The methods of using the system: The application and operation context of the inventory system are described
- E. Tools/Systems/Technologies/Technical Brief: Focus on capturing technical tools, technologies, software, or hardware mentioned
- F. Pros of the system: Advantages and benefits for the stakeholders
- G. Cons of the system: Disadvantages, challenges, and limitations of the system
- H. Findings: Summary of the paper's conclusion on inventory system technology

A Summary of the MS Excel matrix is attached in Appendix 1. Based on the results, five different existing inventory management systems emerged consistently across the literature.

They are:

- Manual systems
- Barcode systems
- RFID systems
- IoT & Sensor-based systems
- AI-enhanced systems

Thus, these five systems are used for the comparative analysis.

2.2 Key Findings from the Comparative Analysis

Retail inventory management systems have faced many changes over the years. Evolving from simple manual recordings (Agboola et al., 2022) to intelligent systems with predictive features (KanmjKsal et al., 2023; Ioannidis, 2025; Pala, 2025). The analysis reveals a critical technological transition driven by RFID, robotics, and sensors, alongside Digital Twin systems that offer strategic monitoring dashboards. Since barcode identification involves a manual, labour-intensive process, RFID introduces the first level of automation in data capture and bulk scanning, which are prerequisites for advanced inventory management systems such as IoT and AI-driven systems (Bhattacharya et al., 2008; Zhou & PIRAMUTHU,

2017). According to Zhou & Piramuthu (2017), bar codes are commonly used to identify class-level items such as product types, material, machinery, and staff at the pallet level, while RFID provides a unique way to identify, track and trace products throughout the supply chain.

Manual and barcode systems present countless scalability issues and challenges, making them unsuitable for rapidly expanding businesses (Kumar et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2022). However, RFID and IoT-enabled systems present effective scalability options for growing retailers (Bhattacharya et al., 2008; Ugbebor et al., 2024). Unlike barcodes, which scale linearly and demand more scanning labour when stock count increases, RFID systems require minimal additional labour as readers can process hundreds of tags simultaneously. Further, another critical benefit provided by RFID is the reduction in inventory shrinkage, caused by theft, loss, or damage via continuous visibility and monitoring of inventory items (Alberto, 2024). Zhou & Piramuthu (2017) also identify that shrinkage results in significant losses that are associated with inventory cost due to both additional holding costs and inflated demand. Accordingly, Zhou & Piramuthu (2017) developed an RFID-enabled tag-based tracking or tracing system featuring a knowledge-based self-adaptive mechanism for the retail sector. Thus, RFID systems are secure, and the ability to implement them at the item-level prevents inventory losses.

Moreover, data quality and accuracy are critical for inventory management systems. Over the years, there has been an evident progression in data quality from manual systems to AI-enhanced systems, which can be considered highly reliable and predictive. Meanwhile, IoT integrated systems record more than 95% accuracy levels compared to basic systems with an accuracy of 70-75% (Ugbebor et al., 2024; Maheshwari et al., 2021). Studies reveal that RFID systems have improved asset tracking and reduced errors, leading to operational efficiencies (Alberto, 2024). In addition, RFID and AI systems ensure planogram compliance, reduce out-of-stocks, and create personalised shopping experiences, making these systems no longer restricted to backroom (Ioannidis, 2025).

Additionally, RFID data can be utilised for consumer preference recognition and service optimisation as well as for running simulations for layout and demand optimisation with Digital Twin integrated systems, which can be used before in-store physical optimisation (Mesquita et al., 2024). Likewise, RFID-enabled inventory management systems can be utilised not only for reactive but also for proactive and strategic operational decisions.

The complexity of implementation varies with the inventory management system used. Various inventory management systems require specialised skills, technological advancement, longer deployment times and greater organisational change management. Traditional and barcode systems require relatively low implementation costs and minimal technical expertise with immediate deployment. Manual systems require training for staff and have greater operational difficulties due to errors in inventory in the long term (Agboola et al., 2022). Barcode systems involve hardware setup, software configuration and staff training sessions on hand-held scanners and operation, which require several weeks for complete operational deployment.

Whereas, RFID-enabled systems require readers, antennas, networking equipment, an electromagnetic environment to ensure optimal read rates, integration with existing systems or implementation from scratch, and training for staff. When it comes to IoT and AI-integrated systems, which are usually built upon RFID with additional components. IoT systems require multiple sensor types, cloud platform configurations and robust network infrastructure. AI enhancements require an additional layer of implementation with data science experts, extensive data preparation and algorithm training in addition to the underlying architecture and devices. Hence, as technological complexities increase, more implementation efforts, organisational coordination and cross-departmental management are required in the retail sector.

Cost and benefits are also critical factors of technological implementation. While manual methods possess lower technological investment costs (Odili & Iheanacho, 2022), in the longer run, they incur the highest long-term operational costs due to errors and inefficiencies (Ugbebor et al., 2024; Saha & Alam, 2022; Odili & Iheanacho, 2022). Conversely, RFID, IoT and AI-enhanced systems require substantial initial cost for infrastructure, development and implementation. Despite the initial cost, AI-enhanced systems can deliver the greatest business value through optimisation and automation over the long term (Ugbebor et al., 2024). In addition, Alberto F. E. (2024, 57) calculates that the payback period and Net Present Value (NPV) of RFID confirm that the benefits of RFID implementation far outweigh the costs. Manual and barcode inventory management systems often rely on periodic audits and are prone to errors and higher labour costs. Conversely, RFID systems automate data collection with continuous, real-time visibility of inventory data, which in turn saves manual interventions, lowers labour costs, and maintains the accuracy level of the

inventory (Alberto, 2024, 56). RFID implemented supply chains have reduced out-of-stocks instances by 16% (Esrar et al., 2023, 2470).

Furthermore, when compared to the costs of IoT & AI inventory solutions, RFID can be considered as a more affordable solution for most medium to large retailers, given the Return on Investment (ROI) in the long run, with the flexibility to integrate easily with other intelligent systems. Nevertheless, based on the retail store size and capital investment capabilities, stores can decide which inventory management system to choose.

This comparative analysis demonstrates that the choice of inventory management method usually aligns with the business size, growth, strategic objectives, technical capacity, and financial capabilities of the retail business. Furthermore, RFID-enabled inventory management systems mark a pivotal step in the retail sector, offering a higher ROI when compared to less cost-effective systems. In addition, RFID systems uncover various avenues for advancing inventory systems with IoT and AI integrations.

3 The Conceptual Digital Twin Architecture

This chapter presents the conceptual Digital Twin architecture (Figure 9) designed to enhance inventory and sales management, AI forecasting, customer activity tracking and real-time shelf monitoring processes in physical retail stores.

The proposed DT architecture integrates RFID and POS data along with AI models to addresses inventory & sales challenges recognized in a physical retail store. Thus, this chapter focuses on the system’s core elements and architecture, showcasing how it integrates these advanced technologies to connect both physical retail activities with digital intelligence.

Figure 9 depicts the conceptual enterprise architecture diagram (enlarged view: Appendix 2), which comprises four main layers. These layers are elaborated in the subsequent sections.

Figure 9. DT Architecture for Retail Store (Created by the author)

3.1 Store and Warehouse Layer

The designed conceptual Digital Twin architecture operates across four primary interconnected layers. The store and warehouse layer functions as the foundational data-

gathering tier of the Digital Twin system. Moreover, both of these digital versions represent the physical retail environment and generate data based on product movements, customer engagement, and purchasing activities. This layer integrates with key subsystems such as Digital Twin Client, RFID scanners, Point of Sale data, Edge Gateway, local database and local backup system. All these components are connected to gather data in real-time and enable quick decision-making at the store level.

The Digital Twin client provides 3D visualisation in real time of the physical store, warehouse, shelf layouts, product placements, and product quantities. This allows staff to monitor activities and make decisions on restocking products and shelf space management. This proposed component functions as a store and inventory management tool with AI-driven recommendations.

Furthermore, RFID and POS are the main sources that provide data for 3D rendering and for predictions. The RFID technology enables continuous tracking of stock levels and customer behaviour. Using this technology, the system is able to capture the data of product movements, interaction duration and shelf activities. Additionally, every transaction which goes through a POS terminal provides real-time records on stock depletion and sales performance. Integrating both data sources into one system delivers a combined view of the active sales and product movements.

Moreover, the Edge Gateway functions as a bridge between the cloud and store systems. It aggregates data from both data sources and performs validation, then transmits events to the main system using a secure API. The local database allows caching of data and provides continuous operations during network outages. It also maintains reliable inventory tracking in offline situations. Accordingly, the gateway implements protocols for data synchronisation, real-time 3D rendering and edge AI processing for latency-critical tasks.

The Monitoring Operations layer consists of a configuration manager and a health monitoring system. Together, these components supervise network conditions, software updates and device health. Additionally, these features improve reliability in operation and foster proactive maintenance. In addition, the Edge framework also supports Industry 4.0 standards, indicating that it is designed for decentralisation and autonomous control.

3.2 Security Layer and Access Layer

The Security and Access Layer establish a secure system by verifying connections and preventing data manipulation. It employs a strategic method based on a Zero Trust Architecture, where neither users nor devices are trusted by default. The Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) limits user actions. Hence, the system only allows login based on role permissions. Additionally, this system requires mutual authentication through the latest version of the TLS 1.3 protocol, a commonly used channel-securing protocol (Arfaoui et al. 2019). Furthermore, corporate user login is verified using federated identity providers such as Azure and LDAP. This approach allows Single Sign-On (SSO) across different parts of the organisation. The Zero Trust Network Access (ZTNA) Gateway validates security protocols by handling and validating all connections from the edge to the cloud based on zero trust principles.

The Security Information and Event Manager (SIEM) subsystem involves continuous monitoring of all system activities, including access events, system events, and policy breaches. Through this approach, the system is able to generate audit logs for event analysis and compliance verification. The Digital Twin framework enables real-time threat detection and automated alerts with the integration of security metrics.

3.3 Corporate Headquarters Layer

The enterprise core resides in the Corporate HQ & Cloud Platform, which unifies data from all stores and their warehouses into one system. This layer comprises various components such as a central AI analytics engine, an Event Bus, a Supplier Portal, a Schema Registry, an IoT device Manager, a Data Lake and a Corporate Dashboard. This integrated system empowers overall management capabilities.

Both the Event Bus and Schema Registry form the foundation for the enterprise's data movement. The Event Bus (e.g. Apache Kafka or Google Pub/Sub) operates as a scalable data pipeline that enables effective and asynchronous communication between the cloud and edge services. The Schema Registry ensures that all messages transmitted through the interconnected systems and devices comply with standardised structures.

The designed Central AI & Analytics Engine components enable data-driven demand forecasting by analysing sales patterns, stock movements, customer behaviour and calendar events. This AI Engine triggers automated restocking requests to the supplier after analysing demand fluctuations and considering external events. In addition, the Corporate Dashboard delivers interactive visualisations of ongoing operations and analytics, enabling users to monitor all retail branches through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and take action accordingly. The Data Lake, which stores both real-time and historical large-scale datasets, supports strategic decision-making through its long-term storage capabilities.

3.4 System Workflow

This section illustrates the dynamic system workflow of the system (Appendix 3), outlining the end-to-end interactions between the corporate cloud and store components. The process begins with the customer interacting with an RFID-tagged cart. When the customer enters the retail store, the tagged cart is detected by RFID scanners installed on the shelves. This detection initiates an event using the Edge Gateway and is tracked until checkout. Subsequently, product purchases made through the POS terminal will be transmitted to the Edge Gateway as encrypted sales data, which is synchronised with the local database. Accordingly, the Digital Twin Client will update the shelf and inventory status in real time with visualisation.

After establishing authentication via a secure tunnel with the security layer, the Edge Gateway sends an authenticated event through the Event Bus to the corporate cloud. Then the sales data and stock data are streamed to the AI Model to analyse trends and generate forecasts. These generated insights will be sent back to the Edge Gateway, including recommendations for shelf arrangement, inventory restocking, pricing strategies and promotions. Meanwhile, the IoT Manager and Health Monitoring system track the device conditions and network performance. Afterwards, the Automated Backup System stores daily snapshots in the local database.

The main aim of this designed architectural view is to provide a scalable and secure foundation for real-world implementation using a Digital Twin. The following chapter focuses on the prototype development after considering the findings from this chapter.

4 Prototype of the Digital Twin

This chapter details the development of a functional Digital Twin prototype for a physical retail store. The prototype integrates a simulated SQLite database and AI-driven demand forecasting with an automated inventory management system visualised within a 3D virtual store and warehouse built in Unity. Heatmaps were incorporated in order to evaluate various shelves performances and visualise sales intensity spatially.

The chapter is structured into four subsections, which will detail the prototype's architecture, followed by the virtual 3D environment, the database design, and the integrated AI model.

4.1 Architecture of the Digital Twin Prototype

The prototype Digital Twin architecture (Figure 10) includes a client layer, data layer, AI server layer and cloud-service layer. The client layer was developed using Unity 3D (version 2022.3.62f1), serving as the front-end visualisation for user interaction. Furthermore, the external client-server framework was built using Python's FastAPI, which is perfect for creating robust APIs quickly. In addition, this technology plays a pivotal role in the field of the Internet of Things (IoT), data analytics, and cloud computing (Giuliani et al.,2025).

Figure 10. Architecture Diagram of the Prototype (Created by the author)

The custom-made database used in the data layer was designed using SQLite in order to simulate a supermarket and its warehouse inventory management. This custom schema generates simulated inventory levels, the store's product catalogues, and sales transactions (Point of Sales). Additionally, the AI server layer was implemented using Python-based analytics tools, and this will be discussed further in the AI model sections.

4.2 Virtual 3D Environment Representation Using Unity

The most dominant 3D design and simulation software in the field of engineering are SolidWorks, CATIA, PTC Creo, AutoCAD, and Autodesk Inventor (Cai et al.,2020). Even though these industry-standard tools are used for engineering and design. With the development of the Digital Twin, engineers tend to use new 3D platforms, which offer free and open-source options (software packages) such as Unity, Unreal Engine, and Blender (Leng et al., 2020; Matulis and Harvey, 2021; Liu et al., 2021). Moreover, Unity has become the leading 3D engine widely used in Digital Twin development, including robotic and industrial applications. For instance, the Digital Twin of Hyundai factory in (HMGICS) Singapore (Hyundai Motor Group, 2023) demonstrates the capability of the Unity engine for large and complex models.

Figure 11. 3D Environment of Store and Warehouse (Created by the author)

Unity, with its gaming industry, supports crucial advantages for Digital Twin projects, with real-time data streaming, AI, and cross-platform integration (Desktop, AR/VR). It also offers real-time interaction required for dynamic simulations over other 3D software like CAD, while 3D asset creation is way more simplified with Blender and Maya tools. Consequently, Unity was selected to create the DT prototype of the retail store after considering its excellent

3D rendering, user-friendly interface, multiple platform support, and extensive range of assets (Singh et al., 2025).

The DT model and structure were created using observational data gathered from visits to a physical store and its warehouse. The prototype 3D environment represents a virtual supermarket store and its warehouse (Figure 11). Further, this 3D prototype contains 2 cashiers' desks, a sushi shop, 4 normal fridge units, a long cooler and 32 store shelves each, with 5 rows. The warehouse holds 7 industrial shelves with location ID and row ID. All this ID were manually created during the database design phase to assign products in exact locations, and these changes were made to demonstrate how both inventory and store could track using an RFID-enabled solution.

4.2.1 Real-Time Products Visualisation

The Digital Twin prototype's core mechanism exists in a `ProductSpawner.cs`¹ class (Figure 12), which supports dynamic product spawning and visualisation by intelligently mapping the inventory database entries to prefabs (3D models).

```
GameObject prefabToUse = isStore ? GetSpecificPrefabForProduct(product) : warehouseProductPrefab;
Vector3 spawnPosition = CalculateSpawnPosition(anchor, i, rowMaxProducts);
SpawnProduct(prefabToUse, spawnPosition, anchor.rotation, anchor, product);
```

Figure 12. ProductSpawner Mechanism

This system uses a multiple lookup strategy, prioritising exact match based on product name, brand, and size, before defaulting to the category. If the matched product's prefab isn't available, this method will automatically assign a default prefab. Besides, the `spacingx` and `spacingz` parameters are used for mathematical positioning for logical product arrangement. The `MaxProducts` constraint prevents product overfilling and maintains real-world density throughout the shelves and rows.

¹ <https://github.com/isurukaldera/ThesisDTPrototype/blob/main/scripts/ProductSpawner.cs>

4.2.2 Interactive Product Labelling and Colour Coding – Visual Intelligence System

The ProductLabel.cs² system was created to provide live feedback on store stock status through a three-colour coding mechanism (Figure13) that converts raw data into visual information.

```
if (product.Quantity >= 80) currentColor = new Color32(0x95, 0xF5, 0x00, 255);
else if (product.Quantity >= 50) currentColor = new Color32(0xFF, 0xFF, 0x00, 255);
else if (product.Quantity > 15) currentColor = new Color32(0xFF, 0x96, 0x00, 255);
else currentColor = new Color32(0xFF, 0x1A, 0x1A, 255);
textMesh.text = $"[product.ProductName] {product.Brand}\nQty: <color=white>[product.Quantity:D2]</color>";
```

Figure 13. Product Labelling Mechanism

This implementation aims to restock the shelf accurately, because if a product is out of stock (OOS) or if a customer cannot find the product on the shelf, this may motivate the customer to switch to another product or buy nothing (Jha et al., 2022). The system component acts as a categorisation system for stock levels using a traffic light system, with green for maximum (80+units), yellow for mid (50-79), orange for low (16-49), and red for critical level (under 15 units). This proposed structure was introduced to facilitate simple identification of stock levels, enabling staff to identify replenishment needs effectively and maintain better shelf availability.

Figure 14. Visualisation of the Product's Health

² <https://github.com/isurukaldera/ThesisDTPrototype/blob/main/scripts/ProductLabel.cs>

In addition, each product has a clearly visualised text label that consists of product name, flavour, size, and real-time quantity, confirming that operational staff can check the health of the quantity efficiently from any viewpoint (Figure 14).

4.2.3 Spatial Anchoring System

An AnchorManager.cs³ component was used to attain precise spatial correlation between the database and the 3D environment. This system acts as a registry for spatial anchors that have been predefined. Each specific shelf ID and row ID is mapped from the database. Whenever products are spawning, AnchorManager.cs leads the system to retrieve the correct transform location and rotation, assuring all of the virtual products are located in their exact real-world placements. This anchoring framework is the backbone for managing the accuracy of the Digital Twin product placement, as it ensures the prototype works like an actual store environment.

4.2.4 HeatMap Subsystem

Due to the decline of customer foot traffic to physical stores, a significant number of stores have shut down across different countries (Kupfer et al.,2024). Although e-commerce websites having become more popular, physical stores continue to play a critical part in direct customer interaction (Senarath et al., 2022). Moreover, the retail industry is dynamic and rapidly evolving, which requires physical retailers to be more inventive and adapt their business strategies according to the competition. A significant gap between physical stores and customers is the lack of an advanced analytics system to enhance efficiency and to improve customer experience. Meanwhile, e-commerce widely leverages analysed data gained through heatmaps to provide personalised recommendations and real-time insights about products (Shili et al.,2024).

³ <https://github.com/isurukaldera/ThesisDTPrototype/blob/main/scripts/AnchorManager.cs>

Accordingly, this Digital Twin prototype was also equipped with a progressive heatmap-generation system (Figure 15) through POS data, renders visual analytics for sales performance across store areas.

Figure 15. Visual Presentation of Heatmaps in the Virtual Environment

The Following are some advantages of the heatmaps:

- i. Provides a concrete understanding of customer behaviour.
- ii. Increases customer engagement by strategically positioning the product and promotion in highly-traffic areas using visualisation and analysis insights.
- iii. Enhances the store layout and changes the layout according to the customer movement pattern.
- iv. Improves inventory management in peak shopping times by using the traffic patterns.
- v. Enhances effective advertising strategies using heatmap data and insights.

Likewise, heatmaps provide very crucial business intelligence for the retail sector to plan the operations, market efficiently, to increase customer satisfaction. Figure 16 showcases the heatmaps mechanism developed.

```
float intensity = Mathf.Clamp01((float)salesCount / maxPopularity);
Color heatColor = new Color(intensity, 0f, 1f - intensity, 0.35f);
float scale = 0.5f + intensity;
GameObject heatmap = Instantiate(heatmapPrefab, anchor.position, Quaternion.identity);
```

Figure 16. HeatMap Mechanism

Furthermore, the developed DT system creates semi-transparent coloured markers over the relevant shelf sections of the virtual store (Figure 15). These markers give an instant visual depiction of sales growth and product demand across various store shelves, by their colour intensity, ranging from blue (weak sales) to red (best sales). Consequently, this real-time analytics overlay of heatmaps onto the existing store operational environment allows staff to identify trends, hot spots by eliminating the gap between data analysis and physical store layout optimisation.

4.2.5 User Engagement and Interactive Features

Beyond the passive visualisation, this prototype includes active user engagement (Figure 17), using the `ProductInteractions`⁴ class. This component is designed for testing the system by clicking on any product in the store. When click the sell button, the `Productinteractions` calls the database manager to simulate a sale, and it will be updated as a sale record in the database in real time.

⁴ <https://github.com/isurukaldera/ThesisDTPrototype/blob/main/scripts/ProductInteractions.cs>

Figure 17. Interactive Features

After the update, the database will notify the ProductSpawner component to refresh and update the three visual dimensions according to the new inventory status, which are product quantity, colour code base on quantity, and the user interface through the UImanager⁵. Subsequently, the recoded sale contributes to the generation of heatmaps.

The main purpose of creating these functions is to demonstrate how this system works with actual customer interaction.

4.3 Database Architecture

The simulated database schema was created after considering two distinct retail scenarios in mind. First, the system required coordinated inventory tracking between the front-end (Store) and the back-end (Warehouse). Second, to align the prototype with actual application, the system incorporated an extensive product catalogue with 350+ products across 10 categories to simulate the complexity of the real-world retail operations. Sample product catalogue data⁶ was created based on the official website of S-Market⁷ in Finland. The simulated Database architecture is extensively described in the following subsections.

⁵ <https://github.com/isurukaldera/ThesisDTPrototype/blob/main/scripts/UImanager.cs>

⁶ <https://github.com/isurukaldera/ThesisDTPrototype/blob/main/Database/database.txt>

⁷ <https://www.s-kaupat.fi/>

4.3.1 DatabaseManager Core - Comprehensive Data Management Foundation

The SQLite simulated database acts as the foundation of the entire system (Figure 18), and all the data operations are routed through the DatabaseManager⁸ component. This central component utilises a refined schema specially designed to support both daily operational needs and advanced analytical capabilities.

```

CORE DATABASE STRUCTURE
StoreShelves: [ShelfID, ShelfName, FurnitureType] // Supermarket layout
WarehouseShelves: [ShelfID, ShelfName] // Storage locations
Products: [ProductID, ProductName, Category, PreferredFurniture] // Master catalog
StoreStock: [ProductID, RowID, Quantity] // Live store inventory
WarehouseStock: [ProductID, RowID, Quantity] // Warehouse storage
StockTransactions: [ProductID, Source, Destination, QuantityChanged] // Movement tracking

ANALYTICAL TABLES
SalesHistory: [ProductID, SaleDate, QuantitySold] // Sales data
DemandForecasts: [ProductID, ForecastDate, PredictedDemand] // Predictions
RestockRecommendations: [ProductID, RecommendedTransfer] // Replenishment

```

Figure 18. Simulated Database

The DatabaseManager maintains a separate but integrated set of tables (Figure. 18) representing retail store and warehouse inventory via an integrated table ecosystem. Through this integrated table ecosystems, which includes StoreShelves, StoreRows, StoreStock, WarehouseShelves, WarehouseRows, and WarehouseStock, the DatabaseManger provides unified and consistent access to all inventory data across the system.

SQL queries are executed through DatabaseManager to manage the database operations. To retrieve complete product information along with spatial data, the GetAllStoreStock() and GetAllWarehouseStock() functions are utilised with JOIN operations across numerous tables.

Further, the RecordSale() function maintains the sales and stock changes by verifying stock availability, adjusting inventory levels, and recording each transaction in the StockTransactions table. This approach offers a complete history that supports various forms of analysis, including operational performance monitoring, sales pattern evaluation, and validation of AI recommendation.

The system uses specialised tables that are controlled by improved techniques in the DatabaseManager class to integrate forecasting capabilities. The GetActivePromotions function queries the promotions table to recognise the active campaigns for AI consideration.

⁸ <https://github.com/isurukaldera/ThesisDTPrototype/blob/main/scripts/DatabaseManager.cs>

The seasonal pattern table is accessed through the `GetSeasonalFactor()` function in order to apply category-specific modification. In addition, the `GetExternalFactors()` method is used to fetch environmental conditions (weather) to advance the demand forecasting. These primary data sources are used as criteria in demand predictions of the AI system.

4.3.2 Physical Store Layout Modelling

The developed database employs an intelligent spatial organisation system which depicts an accurate real supermarket environment. Thus, it starts with the table of `StoreShelves`⁹, which defines the physical furniture structure of the retail market. There are 32 regular shelves allocated for dry goods and non-perishable items, and labels from A1 through A32. Further, 4 refrigerator units (`Fridge1-Fridge4`) for frozen products are necessary for consistent freezing, and 4 cooler units (`Cooler1-Cooler4`) for refrigerated items, which require chilling without freezing. Accordingly, the `FurnitureType` column under the database records the distinct characteristics and capacities particular to each furniture type.

Then the `StoreRows` table continues the spatial hierarchy, breaking down each shelf into individual rows along with specific capacity constraints. Thus, Regular shelves and fridges contain 5 rows each, coolers contain 20 rows to suit smaller, and tightly packed refrigerated goods. Each row has a `MaxProducts` value of 4, signifying the number of unique product variations that can be shown in a row area. Hence, this capacity management ensures the accuracy of reflecting the Digital Twin in real-world space restrictions and prevents heavy visuals in the 3D environment.

Meanwhile, `WarehouseShelves` and `WarehouseRows` tables employ a slightly similar but distinctive spatial organisation. The warehouse is divided into 7 locations (Location A through Location G) with various capacities, which portray realistic storage facility layouts. Location A and Location G contain 8 rows each, representing larger storage areas, while Locations B through F contain 6 rows each for standard storage. Thus, these variations model the actual world instances where warehouse spaces come in various sizes and facilities for efficient mass storage.

⁹ <https://github.com/isurukaldera/ThesisDTPrototype/blob/main/Database/database.txt>

4.3.3 Comprehensive Product Hierarchy

There are over 350 unique SKUs in the product catalogue across 10 categories. The Products table is the master product registry, which contains detailed attributes for each item, including ProductName, Brand, Flavour, Size, Category, and PreferredFurniture. This format supports extensive product management as well as enables intelligent placement decisions based on product characteristics. There are 48 SKUs under the dairy category, including milk, yoghurt products, cheese, and butter products.

These items are modelled as shelf-stable or refrigerated but not frozen items. Hence, each dairy item is assigned to shelf storage.

Further, the database comprises an extensive beverage category with 72 SKUs reflecting the system's capacity to handle complex product variations and brand portfolios. They are divided into subcategories, for instance, water, coffee products, teas, juice and soft drinks. Further, the frozen food category includes 38 SKUs, which are assigned to fridge storage through their PreferredFurniture designation. SKUs sub categories are frozen pizzas, frozen vegetables and ice cream products.

Finally, the meat category is assigned to cooler storage, reflecting proper food safety handling requirements. This contains 30 SKUs, including beef, chicken, pork, lamb, turkey, sausages, bacon, ham, and minced meat variations from HK and Snellman brands.

- Toiletries - 40 SKUs
- Cleaning products - 30 SKUs
- Alcohol - 30 SKUs
- Snacks and confectionery - 40 SKUs
- Bakery items - 30 SKUs
- Pet food - 20 SKUs
- Baby products - 20 SKUs

In addition, the database consists of the above categories, as well as corresponding storage appropriate for each.

4.3.4 Intelligent Product Placement System

The database employs actual retail strategies by using complex category-based shelf alignment logic. This is accomplished via defining which product categories match with which store sections using a SQL mapping system. Shelves are assigned according to real-world practice. For instance, meat products (Coolers), frozen foods (Fridges), dairy items (A1-A3), beverages (A4-A6), alcohol (A7-A9) and etc.

This category mapping is achieved using a SQL query framework that employs window functions and CTE (Common Table Expressions) for smart products allocation based on shelf locations. The system considers category relationships, product movement patterns, and customer shopping behaviours to create logical product relations which present in real supermarkets. For example, of such scenario in retail layout is positioning dairy products near beverages and grouping frozen foods together. These layouts are capable of improving consumer satisfaction and shopping experience while increasing store operations' efficiency (Hübner and Kuhn, 2023).

The actual product placement algorithm uses advanced SQL features, including ROW_NUMBER() partitioning, complex JOIN operations across multiple tables, and conditional logic to ensure products are distributed evenly across available space while maintaining category coherence. Further, the system is implemented with fallback placement logic to find suitable alternative locations while adhering to storage requirements compliance in order to address edge cases where products might not fit in their primary category section.

4.3.5 Advanced Inventory Tracking System

In order to maintain distinction yet synchronised stock records, the inventory management system utilises a dual-location architecture for warehouse storage and store display, including shelves, fridges and other furniture. The StoreStock¹⁰ table keeps records of specific products on furniture and rows of shelf via RowID foreign key, tracking current quantities and recording last restocking timestamps. Therefore, this detailed tracking facilitates accuracy at the furniture level and supports the detailed 3D visualisation in the Digital Twin.

¹⁰ <https://github.com/isurukaldera/ThesisDTPprototype/blob/main/Database/database.txt>

The WarehouseStock table serves a similar purpose for bulk storage, while tracking product quantities and locations within warehouse. This tracking reflects the operational requirements of warehouse inventory management. Quantity fields in both stock tables are updated via transaction processing, guaranteeing data consistency throughout the system.

The product involved, source location (store or warehouse), destination (for transfers), quantity changed, transaction type (sale, restock, transfer), and timestamp-like data are recorded through the StockTransactions table, thus providing a thorough audit record of all inventory movements in the store. This transaction history supports multiple business functions, for instance sales analysis, inventory reconciliation, loss prevention, and performance reporting.

The system applies real-world inventory management principles through the method of Economic Reordering Quantity (EOQ), for various threshold categories based on relevance (Dinçer and Turgay, 2023). When the quantity of a product on a store furniture fall below threshold, then the system triggers the recommendation system to suggest either shelf replenishment from available warehouse stock, or reorder from the supplier before stockouts happen. For example, thresholds are set at category-appropriate levels as follows:

- 25 for high-turnover dairy and beverages
- 15 for space-constrained frozen and meat items
- 10 for slower-moving alcohol and snacks
- 10 for general merchandise

The LeadTimeDays column in the Products table holds supplier delivery timelines used by the AI system to calculate order timing, integrating lead time management. Safety stock calculations are embedded in the AI recommendation logic via the Safety Buffer parameter in the RestockRecommendations table, normally set at 15% to accommodate demand fluctuations and further described in section four.

4.3.6 Realistic Inventory Distribution Algorithms

In order to generate realistic inventory distributions across both retail and warehouse locations in the prototype, the initial database population employs an algorithm. For store stock assignment, the system employs a series of steps:

- i. Firstly, products will be categorised

- ii. Products will be mapped to appropriate shelf sections based on category assignments
- iii. Finally distributes them within those sections using capacity-aware placement logic.

The algorithm utilised creates realistic inventory levels representing actual retail circumstances based on a product's position in a structured sequence.

- High quantities of 80+ units:
 - Products in position 0 of each row cycle (every 5th product)
 - High-volume items
- Medium quantities of 50-79 units:
 - Position 1 products
- Low quantities of 20-49 units:
 - Position 2 products
- Very low quantities of 5-19 units:
 - Assigned to all of the remaining positions

Likewise, this structure creates a realistic inventory system with some products well-stocked and others running low, simulating an actual retail environment where inventory levels vary based on sales velocity and replenishment timing.

The warehouse stock distribution follows a separate logic optimised for bulk storage and space management. Here, quantities range from 180-280 units with variations based on product ID and row location to simulate realistic warehouse inventory patterns. This approach ensures that each warehouse location contains appropriate product categories while maintaining efficient space utilisation.

4.3.7 Enhanced Analytics Foundation

The database is designed not only for simple stock tracking but also to power advanced AI forecasting and analytics of the Digital Twin prototype. Therefore, the database is equipped with several specialised tables to support this aim as described below:

- SalesHistory table
 - foundation for the AI system's demand forecasting algorithms
 - Tracks daily sales data at the product level, including day-of-week and holiday indicators that enable temporal pattern analysis
- RestockRecommendations table
 - Assists both operational execution and retrospective analysis of AI recommendation accuracy and effectiveness
 - Stores AI-generated inventory suggestions with comprehensive context, including prediction timeframes, calculated demand forecasts, current stock positions, specific action recommendations (transfers and orders), safety buffer considerations, and execution status tracking
- Promotions table
 - To track promotional campaigns and their sales impact
- SeasonalPatterns table
 - To track category-specific demand fluctuations throughout the year
- ExternalFactors table
 - To record environmental influences like holidays and weather
- DemandForecasts table
 - To store advanced prediction models

Together, this mock holistic database with all the aspects of the schema supports a robust foundation for data-driven decision making and continuous improvement of inventory management processes for the Digital Twin representing a real-world retail store.

4.4 Prototype AI Model

Traditional physical retail stores are being revolutionised with the merger of Artificial Intelligence, which is primarily applied to analyse customer behaviour and optimise

operations. AI works efficiently across multiple operations in both physical retail stores and online stores, including advertising, automation and POS digitisation. The Amazon Go shop in Seattle uses a smart vision and sensor network for an automated self-checkout system is one of example (Rüschén and Wiehenbrauk, 2017).

Moreover, in the present scenario, AI has a major impact on consumer brand relationships. Retailers can optimise the customer interaction during their shopping with the support of AI tools. For instance, real-time operations like recommendation, product suggestions, and promotions could be done using AI algorithms (Grand View Research, 2024). When retailers can focus on individual customer preferences, it provides a competitive advantage. Further, supply chain management is also a key operation in retail sector that use AI support by many companies in the present, such as DHL, Unilever, Maersk, Walmart and Starbucks. Most of the automated ordering process used by companies' aims are to prevent overstocking and ensure forecasting only based on consumer demand while reducing waste.

In 2021, the AI in the retail market was expected to reach a value of 4.84 billion globally. According to market research projects, this will expand by 23.7 from 2022 to 2030, which indicates the quick adaptation of AI-driven solutions (Praveen Payili, 2025). Additionally, research has shown that an analysis across different retail companies, that use machine learning algorithms for a personalised shopping experience have an average 32% growth in Customer Satisfaction Score (CSAT) with Net Promoter Score (NPS) (Nandigam,2024).

Before the development of this AI model, consideration was given to some issues in traditional retail stores. For instance, holding cost resulting in overstocking, product waste or spoiling and capital immobilisation, which have a direct impact on sales lost, customer frustrations, and negative impact on product brands. The proposed prototype AI model was implemented to tackle the issues with demand forecasting and a real-time alert mechanism for smooth inventory and shelf management by leveraging point of sale data, product promotions, and seasonal trends.

4.4.1 System Architecture and Implementation Framework

The relational SQLite database mentioned in the previous chapter is the foundation for this model, with the SQLite3 Python library acting as the bridge to retrieve input data from the

database (Table 3). This approach ensures streamlined access to stock data and structures historical data that is required for the forecasting algorithms.

Table 3. SQLite Database Tables

Product record	Product catalogue with attributes (product_id, product_brand, category, price, size).
Sale history	Transactional sale record (sale_id, product_id, sale_date, quantity_sold, day_of_week, promotion).
Store stock & warehouse stock	Inventory locations and existing stock.
Promotion	Current and past campaigns.
Seasonal trends	Periods during a year include winter, spring, summer, and fall.
External factors	Holidays and special occasions.

For the API layer, this multi-model forecasting AI model is developed as a RESTful API using the FASTAPI framework and Uvicorn server. This architectural decision was made because REST APIs are ideal due to their lightweight architecture and scalability. Relying on standard HTTP methods (GET, POST, PUT, and DELETE) to exchange JSON- or XML-formatted data (Kelly and Kumar, 2021). The Uvicorn library is a lightweight ASGI (Asynchronous Server Gateway) web server designed for Python applications with the ability to handle operations under a range of load conditions, which makes better solution for the requirements of the prototype forecasting system.

Crucially, Uvicorn allows application logic to concentrate more on business needs rather than infrastructure concerns since its capability of handling server requests, protocol translation and process management. The Python FASTAPI framework is used to create the endpoint for the RESTful API that is used for operations like system management, forecasting and generating recommendations (see Table 4). Beyond that, the system operated ngrok tunnelling technology for secure tunnelling and testing the model in real-world deployment. The integration of these technologies creates a strong, accessible system that facilitates real-time predictions and decision support.

Table 4. API Endpoint References Table

Category	Method	Endpoint	Parameters	Descriptions
Core Forecasting	Post	/recommend	product_id, period_days, historical_weeks, safety_buffer	Past sales data for basic AI recommendation.
	Post	/enhanced-recommend	product_id, period_days, historical_weeks, safety_buffer, include_promotions	Improved recommendation with Promotion and seasonal patterns.
	Get	/demand-forecast/{product_id}	days (30)	Demand forecasting for 30 days.
Data Analysis	Get	/sales-history/{product_id}	weeks (8)	Getting historical sales data for products.
	Get	/product-promotions/{product_id}	-	Getting all product promotions.
	Get	/seasonal-patterns{category}	-	Getting Seasonal patterns for a category.
Performance Analytics	Get	/prediction-accuracy/{product_id}	weeks (8)	Past predictions' accuracy metrics.
	Get	/prediction-confidence/{product_id}	-	Confidence analytics.
Alert System	Get	/critical-alerts/history	days (7)	Critical alert history.
	Post	/test-critical-alert	-	Critical alert testing.
System	Get	/test	-	Health check in the server.

The core analytics engine of the AI server is based on three key Python libraries, including pandas, NumPy and scikit-learn. Together, these allow seamless data processing from raw data to prediction by preserving the information.

- Pandas provides a basis for data analysis and manipulation in the forecasting system. It's particularly suitable for seamless SQL integrations, data-focused data grouping,

and enhanced statistical operations designed to manage large historical datasets through DataFrame operations.

- NumPy supplies the essential computational power for mathematical tasks throughout the entire system by efficiently implementing mathematical formulas. Further, Numpy optimised arrays to support complex statistical calculations and linear algebra, enabling better performance on computation on large datasets and enhancing memory management.
- scikit-learn is utilised within the forecasting ensemble for machine learning algorithms through linear regression implementation to analyse trends. Also, this library offers a reliable implementation of ordinary least squares regression, along with comprehensive metrics for evaluating the model's performance. In addition, its preprocessing capabilities, such as scaling and standardisation, ensure that the well-structured input data is delivered to the forecasting model.

To enhance the demand forecasting, the model integrates with Python's holiday library to accurately identify and account for multiple countries and regional holidays. This enables the forecasting model to incorporate the demand fluctuations with periods associated with calendar events.

Additionally, for the critical alert system, Python's built-in smtplib and email-mime libraries are used to create and send secure email message notifications. This system will send an alert to the user in critical inventory situations.

4.4.2 Mathematical Approach of the Forecasting Engine

Hybrid model or ensemble approaches in AI systems generate more accurate predictions than a single model (Wang et al 2021, Shelatkar et al 2020). Therefore, the forecasting models for this system consist of three types of mathematical approaches¹¹. They are:

- i. Simple Moving Average (SMA)
- ii. Weighted Moving Average (WMA) Linear Regression (LR)
- iii. Python Holidays

¹¹ <https://github.com/isurukaldera/ThesisDTPrototype/tree/main/AI%20Model>

Thus, each of these models is designed to provide more accurate, robust and reliable predictions by acquiring various aspects of sales behaviour before the final prediction.

4.4.3 Simple Moving Average (SMA)

The SMA model stabilises the baseline by calculating recent weekly average sales data (Sarros and Côté 2020). Thus, decreasing the impact caused by daily random fluctuations while holding the overall demand. The mathematical formula can be explained as follows:

$$SMA_i = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^n y_{t-k}$$

This SMA_i indicates the average moving prediction for product (i) wise, where N represents the historical window, as for this model, the time-frame is fixed for 7 days (one week), hence this strategic technique is way better solution to capture the recent trends rather than one-day variations. The recorded sales quantity for one day ($t-k$) is denoted by y_{t-k} and t represents the most recent day. This model is able to predict the estimated measures for short-term demand patterns by using the recent historical average values.

4.4.4 Weighted Moving Average (WMA)

$$WMA_i = \sum_{k=1}^n \omega_k \cdot y_{t-k}, \text{ with } \omega_k = \frac{2k}{N(N+1)}$$

Owing to the fact that only some of the past data is relevant for accurate prediction, this AI hybrid system utilised a WMA forecasting technique. Likewise, this method provides priority to the most recent sales data rather than older data through linearly decreasing weighted (ω_k) over time. WMA is more accurate than simple averaging in FMCG demand forecasting due to its ability to capture short-term patterns (Armen and Jayadi, 2024).

Accordingly, this allows the system to identify rising trends and quickly changing consumer behaviour. The parameter ω_k represents the specific weights assigned to the sales data from days (k) ago. This weighting structured scheme places more demanding on recent data, and

the sum of all weights is constrained to equal one. Consequently, a recent sales trend will have a greater influence on the final forecast as it's multiplied by a coefficient before being added to the total.

4.4.5 Linear Regression (LR)

The main reason why the LR model is better it determines whether the product's sales are steadily rising or declining over a long period, which the WMA and SMA models might miss. In this way, the LR model fits a "trend line" through historical data points (Lindfors, 2021).

Figure 19. Linear Regression Analysis

Using the slope of this trend line allows the system to identify whether product sales ratings are increasing or not (Figure 19). Depending on the established trend, the system will predict the future demand for the product.

$$LR_i = \beta_1 \cdot (X_{max} + h/2) + \beta_0$$

The model predicts the demand by projecting this existing trend into the future. Rather than projecting to the end of the forecasting period, the model uses the midpoint of the forecasting period represented by the projection $(X_{max} + h/2)$, which offers a balanced estimate that considers ongoing trends during the prediction time. The β_0 represents the intercept where the trends theoretically start. While β_1 defines the slope of the trend line. When it's a positive number, that means the sales are growing; or if it's a negative number, the sales are declining.

Using this method, the system calculates the regression line by determining the β_1 and β_0 values that minimise the total difference between the line and all existing data points.

The combined approach of these three models' complementary strengths enhances accurate forecasting. In essence, the SMA provides a stable foundation by reducing the fluctuation each day. Whereas the WMA emphasises current sales patterns to enable rapid adjustments. Finally, the LR model identifies long-term patterns. The integrated method allows for generating demand forecasts with more effective and dependable than single model approaches.

4.4.6 Combination of Predictive Models

Accordingly, this system utilises an ensemble prediction methodology by computing the weighted average of the three models. Likewise, a hybrid model approach has the ability to provide accurate forecasting than any single model alone.

The system allocates influence factor (α) to each model based on performance history and current data conditions.

$$\textit{Final Basline Forecast} = (\alpha_{SMA} \times SMA) + (\alpha_{WMA} \times WMA) + (\alpha_{LR} \times LR)$$

The core principle is that to combine total weight (α) must equal 1, ensuring a realistic prediction. Each model's forecast is multiplied by its corresponding weight, and these weighted results are combined to produce the final prediction (Figure 20). Through this perspective, the system will ensure to give priority for greater influence on the highest reliable models, while low-reliability models have less influence.

Figure 20. Forecasting Result

The final prediction will be an adaptive, well-balanced prediction that combines various viewpoints, including the past patterns, current data conditions and overall trends.

4.4.7 Seasonal and Holiday Formulation

In reality, product demand continually changes with the seasons and holidays. By taking these into account, the system improves a baseline forecast based on a multiplicative adjustment factor to improve products demanding impact on holidays and seasonal patterns, rather than only being based on past and current sales for prediction.

$$\lambda_{\tau} = S(c, m_{\tau}) \times H(\tau)$$

The above formula is the mathematical method of this model; the parameter λ_{τ} (Lambda) represents the final combined scaling factor for the future day, τ (tau). For instance, if λ_{τ} equals 1.3, the expectation of sales is 30% higher than normal day, or if it equals 0.8, sales are expected to be lower by 20%. Further, the $S(c, m_{\tau})$ represents the analysis of the initial sections in the seasonal factor. It addresses the question of what the typical sales pattern during a month (m_{τ}) for a product in a category (c), such as dairy, beverage, snacks, etc. The holiday factor is denoted as $H(\tau)$, and this method is used to find whether the date (τ) is a holiday or not. If it is, the factor will address the question of how much it boosts sales.

As an example, the system will identify a holiday $H("2025-12-25") = 1.4$, showing that Christmas holiday sales will exceed the existing average by 40% higher than a typical day.

4.4.8 Daily Adjustment to a Period Forecast

At this point, a separate adjustment factor is calculated for each day in the forecasting period. It means a one-week forecast based on seven distinctive factors. All of these elements are combined into a comprehensive single adjustment factor, which is applicable for the entire period.

$$\Lambda_{seasonal} = \left(\prod_{\tau=1}^h \lambda_{\tau} \right)^{1/h}$$

When predicting results, adjustment factors were applied in a multiplication manner rather than addition. As an example, using the simple average of two adjustment multipliers that are 1.5 (increase of 50%) and 0.8 (decrease of 20%), yields an average of 15% increase as $(1.5 + 0.8) / 2 = 1.15$. Likewise, this method overestimates and is misleading in the combined impact by suggesting a 15% increase over that time. The accurate combined rate is demonstrated using geometric mean $\sqrt{1.5 \times 0.8} \approx 1.095$, which indicates the daily average growth of 9.5%.

In the Final stage, the adjustment factor formula is added to the prediction system as below.

$$\hat{y}_{final} = \hat{y}_{base} \times \Lambda_{seasonal}$$

The \hat{y}_{base} is the generated preliminary prediction by the ensemble model, which identifies recent sales and sale patterns but doesn't have any connection with the calendar events. The calendar intelligent element $\Lambda_{seasonal}$ operates as an overall adjustment multiplier for seasons and holidays. Accordingly, \hat{y}_{final} is the final context, which integrates both $\hat{y}_{base} \times \Lambda_{seasonal}$ of the prediction and short-term influence to estimate sales for the effective dates.

4.4.9 Inventory Management System

This module converts the AI recommendation into actionable, cost-efficient restocking suggestions while maintaining waste management effectively. Even though the forecasting model could yield statistically accurate predictions, unanticipated swings and supply chain disruptions make it harder to ensure perfect alignment with the actual demand. Thus, in order to mitigate this issue, the system uses a protective buffer as a safety margin.

$$\hat{y}_{target} = \hat{y}_{final} \times (1 + \delta)$$

The formula calculates the required product units' shortage against the current stock level with the safety buffer. When the system forecasts a recommendation on restocking with 100 units, and through this approach, the formula will include a safety buffer $\delta = 0.15$ (15%), which means 115 units. This approach offers three key advantages, including managing demand fluctuation, addressing quality issues and product returns and preventing stockouts. By this method, the system will guarantee that the system retains sufficient inventory coverage for unforeseen fluctuations without causing overstocking.

Moreover, after adding a protective margin to the system. The model will compare the requirement with the current stock level on-shelf availability and warehouse to identify the action that is needed.

$$Shortage = \max(0, \hat{y}_{target} - S_s)$$

After taking both approaches to account (that include both seasonal adjusted prediction and safety buffer), the system will calculate the inventory deficit by matching the target stock level with the current stock on the store (S_s). The *max* function will avoid unwanted restocking by ensuring only actual shortages are recorded. Then the system will suggest how many units should be transferred from the warehouse to the store shelf.

$$Transfer = \min(Shortage, S_w)$$

The calculations will firstly reflect on the store's warehouse to refill the store shelf (Figure 20). To keep the operations feasible, this formula uses the *min* component to make sure that unit transferring never exceeds the current warehouse stock (S_w) or actual shortage.

If the stock in the warehouse is not enough to fill the inventory gap, the system will recalculate the crucial external procedure through the following equation.

$$Order = \max(0, Shortage - Transfer)$$

The final phase estimates the remaining stock units needed to order from the suppliers after transferring the units from the warehouse. The max function system prevents negative ordering, which ensures the model will maintain mathematical consistency even when warehouse transfer surpasses the shortage.

In essence, such a holistic approach offers an economically viable and intelligent replenishment chain which maximises working capital while assuring product availability by converting mathematical computations into real business values. This optimisation is superior for maintaining the warehouse and store inventory stock level. While ensuring accurate demand prediction with the safety buffer to prevent overstocking and stock shortage. The sequential decision-making process, which commences with calculating demands and progressing to utilising internal resources, then engaging with external suppliers, offers cost-effectiveness as well as operational feasibility.

4.4.10 Critical Alert System

The proposed system has a critical alert system that notifies the users automatically in advance about potential inventory shortages. This system monitors all product levels continuously. When any product falls below five units. The system will send an email notification to the users using the smtplib library via Gmail's SMTP server, as an early warning message. Before this trigger, the system automatically checks the following procedures.

- Calculates the existing warehouse stock level with the projected future demand forecasting to identify predictable shortages.
- Evaluates warehouse products' availability for transfer.
- Generates detailed recommendations for internal transfers or external ordering.
- Sends the notification alert to the authorised user, including all important contextual information.

The system operates as an advanced inventory management solution. By covering overall aspects including demand forecasting, stock availability, real-time sales tracking and an advanced warning alert system. Consequently, these enhancements ensure that users are contextually aware of the procedure for imitating the first step to maintain seamless operational service. Even though the SMA method is straightforward and effective for steady demand, it is not suitable for long-term patterns. Identical to WMA, also desirable for detecting short trends, but it is poor at detecting long-term trends. Finally, the LR model excels in capturing fluctuations, whether increasing or decreasing, but is weak with irregular and highly volatile data (Friza and Riyanto, 2024).

5 Finding & Discussion

This chapter outlines the research's key results, contextualising them within the existing literature and evaluating how effectively the thesis achieved its research objectives.

One of the major findings of this research is that the integration of RFID within DT frameworks in the retail industry opens up a transformative way to overcome key inefficiencies in inventory management. The comparative analysis of existing inventory management systems reveals that RFID and DT-integrated inventory management systems increase the efficiency of the retail store stock recording process and are capable of maintaining higher levels of accuracy when compared to other systems. Further, integration of RFID has proven to be a valuable investment for the retail organisation, as it will lay the groundwork to integrate AI, IoT-enabled inventory management systems in future.

The conceptual architecture revealed that DT inventory management systems for physical retail stores can be designed not only as technically robust systems but also ethically considerate. The designed conceptual architecture successfully maps the core components of a DT, which are physical entities, virtual models, and bi-directional data connections as described by VanDerHorn & Mahadevan (2021). Likewise, this conceptual design can be recognised as a GDPR compliant system, eliminating high customer surveillance, yet capable of providing valuable business intelligence insights into customer behaviour via heatmaps and demand prediction AI models. Consequently, the proposed conceptual architecture is able to fill a gap in smart retail while maintaining ethical data practices.

Based on the conceptual architecture, a DT prototype was developed and deployed successfully. Physical retail stores usually face a comparative disadvantage against e-commerce due to a lack of extensive data visibility and real-time customer behaviour information. However, integration of heatmaps into the 3D Digital Twin prototype provides a powerful tool for physical stores to overcome such challenges while increasing the ability to compete with the e-commerce sector. In addition, integration of AI forecasting models into the DT prototype delivers invaluable predictive insights, which may reduce the uncertainty and unpredictable customer behaviour in an ethical way. This finding aligns with the literature proving that hybrid models' capability of mitigating the weaknesses of individual algorithms. The choice of SWA, WMA, and LR was a strategic decision to establish. The successful integration of

an AI model into the DT prototype, along with alerts and inventory logic, justified a path for future improvements with more advanced models like LSTM.

Accordingly, the developed RFID-enabled DT inventory management system is not only a monitoring tool but also can contribute immensely to spatial and strategic planning in privacy-conscious environments. Thus, the principal finding of this thesis is that the proposed RFID-enabled Digital Twin inventory management system for physical stores successfully addresses the current gap in retail operations for a privacy-conscious, competitive tool that can compete with the data analysis power of e-commerce while overcoming key inefficiencies in physical retail inventory management.

6 Conclusion & Suggestions

This thesis has successfully conceptualised, designed and developed of a functional Digital Twin prototype for physical retail, demonstrating its potential to bridge the competitive gap with e-commerce. The research validated that integration of POS data, RFID technology and AI-driven demand predictions, layout optimisation through sales-based heatmaps, and real-time shelf monitoring and inventory visualisation using simulated 3D environment can be achieved while maintaining GDPR compliance. Thus, the developed prototype provides a solid foundation for real-world implementation.

Future work should focus on transitioning this prototype into real-world application with integrated RFID solutions, POS and AI systems. Forecasting features could be enhanced by implementing advanced AI models like Long Short-Term memory (LSTM). Furthermore, integrating Computer Vision such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) could optimise real-time price tagging and automated replenishment. Finally, a dedicated focus on robust security measures is essential to facilitate secure deployment across different retail platforms.

7 Acknowledgement of Limitations

While every effort was made to deliver a systematic and unbiased review during the comparative analysis of existing retail inventory management systems, certain constraints should be acknowledged. The selection of studies for the comparative analysis was done by strict criteria, and researcher bias may occur during the screening, reviewing and data extraction stages. Additionally, the comparative analysis relies on the information and interpretations presented in the secondary literature. Consequently, may vary in terms of methodology and context.

In addition, the 3D environment of the prototype is a conceptual visualisation of a retail store, not a high-fidelity real-world twin. Another drawback is that the developed prototype uses a simulated database rather than actual retail store data due to unavailability of real retail store data, which involves POS and RFID integration.

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Appendix 1. Summary of Comparative Analysis on Inventory Management Systems

	Bibliography	Citation	What are inventory management systems described	How they are used	Tools, systems, technologies, technical brief	Pros of each system	Cons of each system	Findings
1	Inventory management practices at a big-box retailer: A case study. Benchmarking: An International Journal, 30(7), 2458–2485.	Esrar, H., et al. (2023)	JIT, Cross-Docking, CPFR, BRI, ERP, POS, VMI RFID, TPR, Live System, Drones.	JIT: Direct transfer to reduce storage. VMI: Levels are managed by suppliers. Collaborative forecasting, or CPFR. BRI: On-floor vs. stock in the backroom. POS: Gathers sales information. RFID: Products are tracked. Drones: Cycle counting in warehouses.	Web-platforms, Cross-Docking logistics, VMI, CPFR IT systems, BRI classification, ERP systems, POS terminals, RFID system, Drones, TPR reports, real-time monitoring systems.	JIT: Lowers the cost of storage. VMI: Reduces stockouts and increases accuracy. CPFR: Increases forecast precision. BRI: Oversees retail space. ERP: Boosts productivity. POS: Real-time visibility of demand. RFID: Lowers stockouts. Drones: Accelerates counting.	JIT: Disruption-prone. VMI: Requires a supplier. CPFR: Demands a lot of teamwork. Root causes are not resolved by BRI. ERP: Implementation is difficult. POS: Interpreting data is crucial. RFID: Expensive upfront costs. Drones are still developing.	Key elements are essential for JIT and VMI for operations. Two major issues are forecasting errors and human mistakes. Coordination problems arise from RMAs. Adoption of technology enhances visibility. Insufficient advance forecasting impedes effective planning.
2	Inventory Management System for Retail Store. International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science, 05(11).	Aman Kansal & Chiranjeev Kaur. (2023)	Intelligent Inventory Management System, Traditional Inventory Management Solutions.	Managing stock levels, real-time visibility, automate replacement, enabled proactive management, customize strategies, minimize waste, synchronized omnichannel data.	RFID, IoT, Edge Computing, Augmented Reality. User-Friendly Software, Machine Learning, Robotics, Active Pricing, Forecasting.	Prevents stockouts or overstock, reduces human mistakes, enables proactive measures, improves customer experience, is adaptable, and promotes sustainability.	Great primary investment, integration complexity, staff resistance to change, data security/privacy concerns, and ethical considerations.	This research suggests a smart IMS, but as it is a literature review and proposal, it does not contain empirical case study results, efficiency, and forecasting.

3	A Review of Existing Inventory Management Systems. International Journal of Research in Engineering and Science (IJRES), 12(9), 40–50.	Madamidola, O. A., et al. (2024)	Traditional and manual, Automated, Database-Driven, QR-Code, IoT-Based, RFID, NFC, Periodic Review, AI-WMS, Web-Based and Mobile App-Based.	Physical Spreadsheet tracking. Web-Based Browser entree for SMEs. Mobile based Real-time tracking on phones. Physical processes replace by Automated. Real-time monitoring with IoT-sensors. RFID tracking. Automates warehouse operations.	Backend: MongoDB, MySQL. Frontend: Android Studio (Java). Hardware: Barcodes and RFID, Sensors (Ultrasonic, weight). IoT: Cloud. AI: Machine Learning and Computer Vision.	Web and Mobile: Real-time update, User-friendly. Automated: Reduces physical error. IoT/RFID: Real-time data, highly accurate. AI-WMS: enhances decision-making.	Web and Mobile: Security issues, Poor integration approach. IoT/RFID: Expensive, complex integration. AI-WMS: High cost, needs expertise. Barcode: Line-of-sight needed.	The physical system has errors. Automation enhances accuracy & efficiency. IoT and RFID are modern technologies. ERP Integration is a challenge. Cost & expertise are hindrances for SMEs.
4	ROI Analysis of RFID-Based Intelligent Inventory Management Systems. Frontiers in Management Science, 3(3), 52–59.	Alberto, F. E. (2024)	Traditional Inventory Management Systems; IoT (RFID) based Smart Inventory Management Systems.	Traditional methods are manual record keeping and periodic audits. RFID smart system provides real-time visibility, automates replacement, tracks and supports decision-making.	RFID Technology (Tags, Readers, Software, Database), Advanced Analytics, Machine Learning.	RFID system offers real-time visibility, accurate tracking, automated data collection, decreases errors, labour, and shrinkage. Also improves turnover, and reduces stockouts.	Traditional methods are prone to errors, time-consuming, lack real-time visibility, leading to stockouts and overstock. RFID system adds high setup cost, continuing maintenance, risk of being outdated, complex integration, security concerns.	RFID advantages include minimizing labour, shrinkage, and improved accuracy. ROI calculations demonstrate economic viability. Profit is short, NPV is positive.
5	Identification reduction in inventory management: An RFID-based solution. Records of Operations Research, 258(2), 285–300.	Zhou, W., & Piramuthu, S. (2017)	Traditional Inventory Management Systems, IoT-driven Inventory Management Systems.	Traditional method used Barcodes scanned at POS/counts for categorical-level tracking. RFID Tags read without sight and support adaptive results, detects switching.	Traditional method uses Barcode and scanners, RFID Tags (passive and active), readers, middleware, ML algorithms (WMS).	RFID provides Real-time visibility, reduces mistakes, detects ticket-switching, adaptive learning, and enhances accuracy.	Traditional approach is prone to identification loss, physical errors, no real-time visibility. RFID adds higher initial cost, complex integration, continuing maintenance, data concerns.	RFID enables adaptive learning that allows intelligently modify policies to minimize inventory loss. Protecting less expensive items is a key to prevent ticket-switching.

6	Automated Inventory Management Systems with IoT Integration to Optimize Stock Levels and Reduce Carrying Costs for SMEs: A Comprehensive Review. Journal of Artificial Intelligence General Science (JAIGS), 6(1), 306–340.	Ugbebor, F., et al. (2024)	Traditional or Manual system, IoT-Integrated Automated system, Cloud-based AI/ML-Enhanced system.	For real-time monitoring, automate data gathering, improve demand forecasting, enable automated reordering, facilitate info flow with ERP, predictive maintenance.	IoT Sensors, Cloud Computing, Real-Time Analytics, Machine Learning, Edge Computing, ERP Systems, Predictive Analytics, Neural Networks.	IoT-Integrated: accuracy, reduces safety stock, labour costs, stockouts. Cloud-Based: Reduces IT costs, improves reliability. AI/ML: enhances demand forecasting.	Significant capital investment, Technical knowledge is required, Issues with system capabilities, organizational resistance, and dependence on phased implementation.	Implementation illustrates significant gains in stockouts, accuracy and cost effective. ROI in 12-18 months is positive. Important success factor includes training, management change, and architecture.
7	Review of Modern Inventory Management Techniques. Global Journal of Business & Management, 1(2).	Aro-Gordon, S. & Gupte, J. (2016)	Inventory Management and Stock Organization (general concepts).	To supervise supply/storage/ accessibility, Ensure flow of goods, set stock levels (ROL, MAL, etc.), classify inventory (ABC), reduce costs, and guarantee timely delivery.	Software Applications, Mathematical formulas, ITR, ABC Analysis, JIT, VMI, and quantifiable models such as ROL, MAL, EOQ.	Stock Levels/EOQ: Guarantees optimality. ABC: Focuses on valuable items. JIT: Avoids excess inventory. VMI: Lets customer focus on demand. Software: Saves costs, reduces stockouts.	General: Poor computerization, unskilled employees. JIT: Dependent on timely deliveries from supplier. VMI: Customer gives up direct oversight. Bulk-Purchasing: Needs additional storage space.	Twelve key inventory management techniques were condensed. The selection relies on the enterprise. Advantages encompass enhanced cost – effectiveness, productivity and quality service. Appropriate inventory management avoids low capital and reduces costs.
8	Development of a web- based platform for automating an inventory management of a small and medium enterprise. fudma journal of sciences, 6(5), 57–65.	Agboola, F. F., et al. (2022)	Manual; Web-Based; Computerized (the developed system).	Physical: Track stock, create Purchases orders, and write reports. Developed System: Manage sales, products, categories, track stock & transactions, Generate reports & profits analysis.	Iterative Waterfall Model; MySQL; phpMyAdmin; Modules: Sales, Product, Category, and user Management.	Developed System: User-friendly, efficient, improves service, reduces stress, saves time, faster processing, accurate, secure.	Manual: Labor-intensive, expensive, error-prone, time-wasting, excessive paperwork, inefficient.	Manual systems present several issues. The web-based system that has been developed provides efficiency, enhanced security, and more accurate data processing compared to manual processes.

9	Artificially Intelligent Warehouse Management System. Asian Journal of Basic Science & Research, 03(03), 16–24.	Alangari, S., & Ahmed Khan, N. (2021)	Manual; Artificially Intelligent System.	Manual: Manual inputs, checks, and reporting. AI System: User access; manager handles entries & requests; generates reports & predictions; automated approvals.	AI heuristics; Web-enabled; DBMS (e.g., MySQL); Role-based access; Predictive analytics; Automatic reporting.	AI System: Smart & effective management, quick fixing, advance notifications, better prediction power.	Manual: Time wasting, error-prone, no automatic reports, difficult to search and manage.	Manual systems are inefficient. Using a proper DBMS with web-based AI System offers effective demand forecasting and automated inventory management system.
10	Design of Inventory Management Information System Using Periodic Review Method. E3S Web of Conferences, 448, 02010.	Alim, I. F. H., & Isnanto, R. R. (2023)	Manual; Basic Information System; Periodic Review System; Integrated System; EOQ & ROP.	Manual: Data observation & reports. Developed System: analyses usage data to recommend refill quantity/timing; outputs parameters (R, s, S); displays graphs.	Waterfall SDLC; Flutter based Mobile & Web (Laravel/PHP) apps; REST server; Periodic Review algorithm.	Periodic Review System: reduces costs, simplifies ordering process, suitable for intermittent demand, and provides refill advice.	Manual: Time wasting, inefficient, no prediction. Basic System: Only records data, no recommendation.	Manual systems lack efficiency. The developed periodic review system was effectively put into practice, validated, and proves beneficial for making cost effective choices regarding to stock replacement.
11	Development of An IoT-Based Inventory Management Solution and Training Module Using Smart Bins. *13th Conference on Learning Factories, CLF 2023*.	Chukomin, A., et al. (2023)	Kanban; iBin; DProdLog Smart Bin; Advin System; IoT-based Smart Bin (Author's).	Kanban: Manual or card-based replenishment. Author's System: Real-time consumption monitoring; triggers replenishment; data analysis for bottlenecks; used for training.	Smart bins with weight sensors; IoT-Hub; Cloud platform; TOC/DBM algorithm; AI algorithms.	Author's System: Geometry-independent monitoring, real-time data integration, flexibility/transparency, bottleneck identification, easy installation, combines Kanban & AI.	Kanban: Lacks transparency, stressful throughout demand changes. Author's System: Applicable only in manual warehouse settings.	When IoT Smart Bins combined with TOC/DBM enhances visibility, facilitates real-time optimization, and pinpoint areas of inefficiency. Also, effective training module was developed.
12	Stock Management Using IOT. International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews, 3(6), 3657–3663.	Daftarband, A., et al. (2022)	RFID-based System; Smart Shelf; RFID+ZIGBEE System; Ultrasonic Sensor-based (Author's).	Author's System: Monitors box count using distance; sends email alerts for low stock.	NodeMCU ESP8266; HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor; ThingSpeak; IFTTT.	Author's System: Accurate, cost-effective, remote access, reduces human interaction, automatic alerts system, easy to install.	RFID+ZIGBEE: Limited tracking range, difficulty reading multiple tags.	The author's proposed system, utilizes ultrasound technology provides an affordable and effective method for automatic stock tracking and offers remote access and alerts.

13	Auto Parts Inventory Management System. International Journal of Scientific and Management Research, 06(09), 314–329.	G. Llabres, E. (2023)	Manual (Paper/Excel); Computerized System with QR.	Manual: Physical counting, paper records. Developed System: Register/delete/modify items; store supplier info; view stocks; QR code scanning; process sales.	Windows OS; VB.NET; XAMP P; MySQL; QR Code Scanner.	Developed System: User-friendly GUI, real-time monitoring, fast/accurate, secure, and simplifies retrieval.	Manual: Unreliable, time/money waste, inaccurate data, error-prone.	The manual approach had considerable issues (100% effect on unpredictable tracking), while the proposed system received a very good rating for all aspects of the ISO 25010 evaluation.
14	Smart Warehouse Management System. Machines , 10(2), 150.	Khan, M. G., et al. (2022)	Manual/Partially Automated; RFID-based; Barcode-based; IoT-based Smart WMS (Proposed).	Manual: Paper-based, delayed updates. Proposed System: Real-time detection via RFID/barcode at nodes; MQTT data transfer; instant updates; order verification.	ESP32; RFID/Barcode readers; Raspberry Pi (MQTT broker); MQTT protocol; Angular; .NET; SQL Server.	Proposed System: direct updates, 79% faster storing, low level latency/power, resilient, modular, scalable.	Manual: Inefficient, no real-time tracking or updates, error-prone, delayed updates. Barcode: low reliability, requires line-of-sight.	The suggested system brought 79% of reduction in time which required to store goods and update time from 24h to minutes. MQTT proved to be more effective than HTTP/S, resulting 88% improvement in system efficiency.
15	Inventory and Bill Management System. International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology, 4(3), 512–520.	Mr. Aditya Vaibhav Pawar & Mr. Nilesh Vishwas Patil. (2024)	Manual Processes; Inventory and Bill Management System (Proposed).	Physical: Paper-based tracking, invoicing, billing. Proposed System: Automatic stock tracking, invoicing, reporting, customer management, and returns.	.NET Core 6; MS SQL Server; Windows 11.	Proposed System: Improves efficiency/accuracy, streamlined operations, scalable, valuable insights, secure, and user-friendly.	Manual: Inefficient, error-prone, lack of real-time data, difficult to scale.	The manual method was ineffective. The suggested system effectively automated inventory tracking and billing, while offering valuable insights for decision making.
16	Automated Inventory Control System for a University Cafeteria Management. Anchor University Journal of Science and Technology, 3(1), 169–178.	Odili, J. B., & Iheanacho, U. (2022)	Manual; Barcode; RFID; WMS; Proposed Automated System.	Manual: Physical recording/tracking. Proposed System: manage goods movement without human interaction; real-time status tracking; add/view/search inventory.	Python; Visual Studio; Object-oriented database.	Proposed System: Real-time status updates, reduces workload, saves time, secure, reduce errors, generates accurate reports, increases profit.	Manual: Prone to errors, slow, easy to operate, labour-intensive, expensive.	The manual cafeteria system contains several issues. The suggested system increases profit, updates in real time and automates tracking.

17	Smart Management Scheme for the Efficient Control of Industrial Inventory. American Journal of Industrial and Business Management, 12(04), 519–530.	Saha, P., & Alam, Md. A. (2022)	Manual; Fully Automated IMS; ERP; Suggested Inventory Database System.	Manual: Unfriendly reports, hard to track. Proposed System: Automatically calculates EOQ/ROL; updates inventory; sends warning on low stock status; manages purchase/sales data.	Visual Basic 2017; SQL Server.	Proposed System: Affordable, efficient/reliable, decreases errors/stockouts, versatile, automatic analytics, secure.	Manual: Expensive, error-prone, leads to stockouts. Fully Automated IMS: Very expensive to implement.	The software suggested effectively manages data, address stockout issues, and cost-effective. It improves customer satisfaction and recommended for franchise chains.
18	Inventory Management System Using Mobile Application. International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology & Science, 3(3).	Sampath Kumar S, et al. (2021)	Manual: Paper-based; Desktop Application and Mobile Application (Proposed).	Manual: Physical tracking through notebooks. Proposed System: Detects sales/inventory using mobile; multi-profile, auto profit/loss; reorder alerts; cloud sync.	Mobile App (Android); SQLite; Cloud Storage; OAuth.	Proposed System: Removes paperwork/ reduces errors, portable, real-time updates, secure backup, auto analytics, multi-business.	Manual: Tiresome, risk of data loss, time wasting, needs employees. Desktop App: Need a PC for access.	The mobile application uses cloud computing to ensure real-time update and data backup, simplifies operations, while offering portable and secure benefits for small vendors.
19	Design and Development of An Inventory Management Mobile Application. International Journal of Research in Engineering and Science (IJRES), 11(9), 38–47.	Sheng, T. E., & Harun, H. (2023)	Manual; Automated System; Mobile Application (Developed).	Manual: Physical counts & recording in logbooks/spreadsheets. Developed App: Store/view inventory /edit; record purchases/sales; automatic update levels; search; reports; low-stock alerts.	RAD methodology; UML; Flutter; JomHosting backend.	Developed Application: enhances efficiency, avoids data loss, reduces error, real-time access, low-stock alerts, useful & easy to use.	Manual: Time wasting, error-prone, data loss risk, no real-time visibility, inefficient.	Manual processes are inefficient. The suggested app provides both user-friendly and helpful features. User interface enhancements need to recover errors and visual appeal.
20	Design and implementation of a new intelligent warehouse management system based on MySQL database technology. Informatica, 46(3).	Zhang, Y., & Pan, F. (2022)	Intelligent Warehouse Management System (Developed).	Developed System: Manages basic info, system, procurement, warehousing, and inventory. Provides automatic records and real-time information.	B/S Architecture; MySQL; Eclipse; Struts2, Hibernate, Spring; Java; Tomcat.	Developed System: Improves efficiency/management level, automatic records, real-time info, runs normally, meets user response time.	General Context: Disorganized warehouses, inefficient management, low info integration in domestic enterprises.	The system successfully realizes the five core warehouse modules, runs normally, meets test requirements, and improves management efficiency.

<p>21</p>	<p>Kellermayr-Scheucher, M., Horandner, L., & Brandtner, P. (2022). Digitalization at the Point-of-Sale in Grocery Retail - State of the Art of Smart Shelf Technology and Application Scenarios. <i>Procedia a Computer Science</i>, 196, 77–84.</p>	<p>Kellermayr-Scheucher et al. (2022)</p>	<p>Smart Shelf Systems (Image Recognition-based, Sensor-based)</p>	<p>Out-of-Shelf Detection: Monitors when shelves are empty in order to send out alerts for restocking. Compliance: Guarantees that the products are located with the appropriate quantity facing forward. Restock-Level Monitoring: Tracking stock levels and alerting employees when it falls below a set threshold. Theft Detection: identifying possible risks by using real-time weight calculations to analyse removed quantity. Inventory Optimization: Employs gathered data to improve stock level on shelves and within store. Consumer analytics: Tracks customer behaviour through dwell time, picking, and returning.</p>	<p>Core Technologies: computer vision, IoT Sensors, RFID, weighing sensors, infrared sensors LiDAR, Laser. AI & Data Processing: Self-study algorithms for shelf tracking, data analysis, and Forecasting planning. IT Architecture: Mainly relies on cloud solutions, supplemented by some local PC/edge computing; gateway computers are utilized transfer data from hardware to cloud. Hardware Components: Fixed or ceiling-mounted cameras, smartphones and tablets, weight sensors, pushers or hooks, RFID antennas, sensor rails, price rails, along with light sensors. These components are designed for easy integration into existing shelves</p>	<p>Computer vision: Identifies exact product, enabling precise planogram matching. Lower hardware investment cost compared to full sensor coverage. Offers reduce investment expenditure on hardware compared to complete sensor coverage. Sensor-Based Systems: Provides ongoing real-time tracking of shelf stock. While providing accurate and real-time inventory data tracking to identify unusual stock movement.</p>	<p>Computer vision: Monitoring is not continuous (only works when image is taken). poor lightning and reflecting surfaces Mist, and similarly products packaging. Difficult to recognize small products. Sensor-Based Systems: Depends on logic and algorithms; Unable to identify particular products. The effectiveness is compromised with unpackaged or loose items like fruit and vegetables due to natural variance in weight moisture content. The longevity of sensor can be impacted by extreme temperature (e.g., in bake-off or frozen areas).</p>	<p>The primary technology categories differ: Computer vision is used for product identification, whereas sensor-based systems monitor changes in quantity. Significant technical limitation including fresh produce, bake goods, and frozen items. Also, most systems are not universally applicable. Sensor fusion is becoming more popular, such as cameras and weight detectors, is observed to address the drawbacks of single technologies and enables new use cases like automated checkout. Technical requirements include lighting conditions, shelf layouts, and products packaging.</p>
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22	Villegas-Ch, W., Navarro, A. M., & Sanchez-Viteri, S. (2024). Optimization of inventory management through computer vision and machine learning technologies. <i>Intel ligent Systems with Applications</i> , 24, 200438.	Villegas-Ch et al. (2024)	Computer Vision-based Inventory Management Platform	Automated product classification and detection from images in real time. Accurate inventory counting, especially in large-stocks. Automated notification for stock level monitoring and discrepancies. Forecasting of future stock needs based on historical data. Seamless and immediate data synchronization with current inventory management systems (IMS).	Computer vision (CNN), RESTful APIs, Python, Pytorch, Tensorflow, and OpenCV. Cloud-based solution with edge computing capabilities. Semi-supervised learning for image labelling, data augmentation (rotations, scaling, and lightning and contrast adjustments), and hyperparameter enhancement through Bayesian optimization are examples of data processing techniques.	Through the optimization, the system provides instant stock replenishment and inventory counting with higher accuracy in product identification. It provides automated monitoring and real-time data synchronization. It enables self-learning to recognize new products, while facilitating proactive management via forecasting for restocking.	Image quality affects tracking accuracy, especially in condition with poor lighting, reflective, and fogged glass. The technical integration is complex because of custom API development and potential encountering issues with old IMS systems. Also requires a high computational power for real-time processing. The effectiveness of the algorithms is also affected by some factors including unpacked items, loose items, similar items, small items, fruits and vegetables.	Compared to early techniques, the CNN technology proved its higher accuracy and resilience, while decreasing counting mistakes. Its streamline architecture facilitated fast processing and fewer discrepancies. Although the proposed AI model has effective outcomes, the system integration and real-world conditions show the biggest implementation challenges.
23	Saccomanno, F.P., Trivella, A., & Guerriero, F. (2025). Integrated sales planning for in-store retail: A multi-stage stochastic optimization approach. <i>European Journal of Operational Research</i> .	Saccomanno et al. (2025)	Demand elasticity formulation, scenario tree creation, multi-stage stochastic linear programming (MSLP) model, and integrated assortment, inventory, and promotion optimization.	Coordinated planning of product control, shelf arrangement, marketing campaigns, choice of items, and stock management over multiple periods, considering unpredictable demand.	Multi-stage Mixed-Integer Stochastic Linear Program, Geometric Brownian Motion (GBM), Discrete scenario, Linear coefficients, Gurobi v11 and Python.	Explicitly address uncertainty through the use of scenario trees. Captures decision interconnections and measures the effect of promotional activities on customer demand. Feasible for practical and real-world situations for an instance tactical planning. Also offers flexible method for creating scenarios.	Rapid growth requires historical data in order to operate with scenarios, products and categories. It functions effectively in limited scenarios but proves progressively challenging and less efficient as the scale and complexity grow. Therefore this method is most suitable for smaller-scale operations.	The proposed optimization approach offers greater profit. Effectively modelling customer demand was a major factor in its success, as it's identified as solution close to optimal with efficiency. While the approach performs strong on problems of typical complexity but its effectiveness decrease when cope with large-scale scenarios.

24	Soret, A., Martinez-Botí, A., Marcos-Matamoros, R., Gonzalez-Reviriego, N., Roura-Adserias, F., Palma, L., Benito Martín, S., & Gonzalez-Ubierna, S. (2025). Sub-seasonal and seasonal climate predictions for a sporting goods retailer company: Co-development of a climate service from scratch. <i>Climate Services</i> , 39, 100583.	Soret et al. (2025)	Climate service for retail; Sub-seasonal and seasonal forecasting system; Co-developed tool designed to aid decision-support for inventory management, staffing, and promotional strategies.	Integration probabilistic climate forecasts in to planning workflows supports to improve stock levels, warehouse distributions, staffing, and promotional campaigns. This method offers decision making on seasonal factors.	Technologies: ECMWF SEAS5 (seasonal), NCEP CFSv2 (sub-seasonal), ERA5, Rankine probability Skill Score (RPSS), Brier Skill Score (BSS), UX design and Python/CDS-API	Facilitates Proactive inventory and staff planning, Minimizes the risk of overstock and stockouts due unpredictable weather patterns, provides various forecasting according to periods (weeks and Months), Promotes environmental responsibility via streamlined logistics.	User pattern forecasting is challenging because it needs higher training and engagement. Integrating sub-seasonal and seasonal products presents significant complexity.	Seasonal based forecast increase sales in test stores while gaining user trust. The developed system provides enhanced recommendation in retail planning.
25	Liu, Y., Kalaitzi, D., Wang, M., & Papanagnou, C. (2025). A machine learning approach to inventory stockout prediction. <i>Journal of Digital Economy</i> , 4, 144–155.	Liu et al. (2025)	ML system designed to predict stockouts; Utilizing conventional ML models for inventory management; Data-driven strategy for effectively managing extensive and unbalanced SKU datasets.	The system aims to forecast stock events through current inventory quantities, past sales records and demand forecasting. This also facilitates proactive restocking, safety stock buffer, and efficient inventory management within retail supply network.	Technologies: Support Vector Machines, Logistic regression, AdaBoost, XGBoost, Gradient Boosting, SMOTE + Tomek Link, AUC-ROC, Python.	Manages extensive and highly imbalanced datasets. Enhances better stockout prediction accuracy than traditional techniques. Provides understandable insights into feature importance, Delivers better results through robust and traditional ML models. Suitable for continuous inventory monitoring and adaptive stock replenishment.	Only limited to traditional ML Approach instead of deep learning and it mostly depends on data preparation. The model's success is reliance on quality of the data, choice of features, careful tuning, and the performance of different algorithms varies greatly.	Current stock levels and short-term demand forecasting provides effective outcomes with the Random Forest model. This approach effectively manages the challenges of imbalanced data, while improves real-world inventory management strategies to avoid stockouts.

26	Galdelli, A., Pietrini, R., Mancini, A., & Zingaretti, P. (2024). Retail Robot Navigation: A Shopper Behavior-Centric Approach to Path Planning. IEEE Access, 12, 50154-50164.	Galdelli et al. (2024)	Robotic inventory system to track customer behavior; Shelves inspection and planogram compliance using autonomous robots; Layout planning through the heatmaps and user interaction.	Checks inventory through shelves images, Autonomous navigation within retail environment, verifies product placement adheres to the planogram, identifies stockouts using customer historical and real time data.	Technologies: Tiago-Base (simulation), StockBot (real-world), UWB tags, RGB-D cameras, 2D LiDAR, Heatmap-TSP, Quadtree decomposition, ROS, GAZEBO, Or-Tools.	Decreases the need of human interaction and enhances accurate inventory records. detects customer behaviour pattern through foot traffic, Enables continuous tracking product arrangements. Able to function effectively in both simulated and real-world settings.	Customer tracking is limited, requires existing layout of the store and shelves, Initial investment is high, Effectiveness depends on the accurate sensor data and condition of the store environment. It does not provide real-time data, also heatmaps are generated through the historical data.	The Heatmap-TSP system enhances robots navigation routes through the customer behaviour data, leading to a significant increase in survey efficiency in the active retail settings. Also, open-source code facilitates widespread use.
27	Arvind, V. R., Shrinidhi, R. M., Deepa, T., & Maheedhar, M. (2025). Intelligent Warehousing: A Machine Learning and IoT Framework for Precision Inventory Optimization. IEEE Access, 13, 169381-169414.	Arvind et al. (2025)	System for tracking Inventory through IoT-Edge and ML. Digital Twin Frameworks powered by synthetic Data, Software-defined architectures for the Internet of things including SD-IoT, SD-IoV, SD-IoMT. Warehouse Management System (WMS)	The proposed system designed for accurate inventory management including smart system, real-time operational control, proof records, synthetic data for training purposes, and for AI for logistics optimization.	Technologies: XGBoost, LSTM, Isolation Forest, Reinforcement Learning (RL), RFID Tags, Smart Shelves, Environmental Sensors, LiDAR, Robotics, Drone, Blender, Nodes, and Blockchain, Pytorch, TensorFlow, scikit-learn, OpenFlow, Warehouse Optimization Architecture (WOA).	This suggested system achieved highest inventory accuracy while reducing stockouts and overstock. It supports secure and scalable machine learning training. Also, it mitigates fraudulent activates by providing supply chain visibility.	Requires significant upfront investment, Risk of IoT signal getting block and overload data, Skill gaps and employees may ignore the changes, Susceptible to cyber-attacks, integration with Warehouse Management System has considerable challenges	This system reduces forecasting errors and significantly cuts operational costs. Through the synthetic data it provides effective model training, while offering real-time device control. The blockchain integration also reduces waste; robotic automation reduces labor operations and increases storage density.

Appendix 2. Conceptual Corporate Digital Twin Architecture

Appendix 3. Conceptual Corporate Digital Twin Sequence Diagram

Appendix 4. Conceptual Digital Twin Architecture Clear View

Appendix 5. Conceptual Customer Tracking Sequence Diagram

Appendix 6. Prototype Digital Twin Class Diagram

Appendix 7. Prototype Digital Twin Sequence Diagram

Appendix 8. AI Declaration

Declaration of AI Usage

Student ID number: 002213552

First name: Isuru

Last names: Hollupathirage

Degree Programme: Digital Systems and Service Development

The title of the thesis work in English: A Digital Twin System for Retail Inventory & Sales Management

Supervisor: Associate Professor Annika Wolff

I, the undersigned, in line with LUT AI usage recommendations and policy (<https://elut.lut.fi/en/completing-studies/rules-and-regulations/ai-based-tools-policies>) hereby declare the following regarding the usage of AI tools in the development of the contents of my thesis work:

1a) AI Tool Name: Grammarly

1b) Purpose of Use: Grammar Check

1c) Detailed explanation of how and in which sections the tool was used: To check Grammar mistakes in Methodology

1a) AI Tool Name: Copilot and DeepSeek

1b) Purpose of Use: Understanding the Concepts

1c) Detailed explanation of how and in which sections the tool was used: tools were used to search information about IoT, Understand Concepts, and to test own knowledge.

I declare that no other AI assistance or tools were used in the development of the contents of my thesis work than the above mentioned.

I, the undersigned, in line with LUT AI usage recommendations and policy (<https://elut.lut.fi/en/completing-studies/rules-and-regulations/ai-based-tools-policies>) hereby declare that no AI assistance or tools were used in the development of the contents of my thesis work.

Date: 28.11.2025

Signature: Isuru Hollupathirage